

शिक्षा रूपान्तरण : समावेशिता, नवप्रवर्तन र समृद्धिको बाटो
Education Transformation: Path to Inclusion, Innovation and Prosperity

Book of Abstract

राष्ट्रिय शिक्षा सम्मेलन-२०८२
National Education Conference-2082

स्थान : जनकपुरधाम, मधेश प्रदेश
मिति : २०८२ असार १० र ११ गते

शिक्षा हाम्रो अधिकार हो, समावेशी शिक्षा हाम्रो प्रतिबद्धता हो
Education is our right, inclusive education is our commitment

मधेश प्रदेश सरकार
शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालय
जनकपुरधाम, मधेश प्रदेश

“शिक्षा रूपान्तरण: समावेशिता, नवप्रवर्तन र समृद्धिको बाटो”
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संरक्षक

माननीय, रानी शर्मा तिवारी, मधेश प्रदेश शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्री

प्रमुख अतिथी

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NARC- प्रतिनिधि

NAST- प्रतिनिधि

PRI- प्रतिनिधि

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(Patent 16⁺; Copyright 25⁺; Peer Review 250⁺; Book 32⁺)

पृष्ठभूमि

शिक्षा सामाजिक र आर्थिक विकासको आधारशिला भएकाले कुनै पनि समाजमा परिवर्तनको प्रमुख चालकको रूपमा यसलाई लिईन्छ । नेपालमा, क्षेत्रीय विविधतालाई सम्बोधन गर्दै राष्ट्रिय एकता कायम गर्न शिक्षाको महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका रहेको देखिन्छ । आफ्नो समृद्ध सांस्कृतिक र सामाजिक सम्पदा भएको मधेश प्रदेशले राष्ट्रिय शैक्षिक लक्ष्यहरूसंग तालमेल गर्दै स्थानीय आवश्यकता र आकांक्षाहरूलाई सम्बोधन गर्ने बलियो शैक्षिक पारिस्थितिक प्रणाली (Ecosystem) निर्माण गर्ने महत्वलाई मान्यता दिएको छ । गत आर्थिक वर्षको अषाढ महिनादेखि मधेश प्रदेशले शिक्षा नीति निर्माण कार्यको माध्यमबाट नतिजा मुलक मधेश प्रदेश शिक्षा नीति, २०८१ निर्माण गरेको थियो । विशेष गरी उच्च शिक्षा, माध्यमिक शिक्षा, प्राथमिक शिक्षा लगायत वालविकास केन्द्र, कृषि शिक्षा र नीति निर्माणमा प्रादेशिक स्वायत्ततामा केन्द्रित पहलहरू मार्फत महत्वपूर्ण प्रगतिको अपेक्षा गरेको थियो । यी प्रयासहरूको बावजुद, गुणस्तरीय शिक्षामा पहुँच, शिक्षण प्रशिक्षण र पाठ्यक्रम स्थानीय र प्रदेशको सामाजिक- आर्थिक यथार्थमा सान्दर्भिकता जस्ता क्षेत्रमा चुनौतीहरू कायमै रहेको देखिन्छ । यीनै चुनौति वा समस्याहरूलाई समग्र रूपमा सम्बोधन गर्न, मधेश प्रदेशले यस क्षेत्र र राष्ट्रको शिक्षाको भविष्यका बारेमा छलफल गरी रणनीति र सहकार्य गर्न विभिन्न क्षेत्रका सरोकारवालाहरूलाई एकसाथ ल्याएर राष्ट्रिय शैक्षिक सम्मेलन आयोजना गर्न लागेको छ ।

राष्ट्रिय शैक्षिक सम्मेलनका उद्देश्यहरू

- **वर्तमान शैक्षिक परिदृश्यको मूल्याङ्कन गर्न** : मुख्य सफलता, चुनौती र अवसरहरू पहिचान गर्दै मधेश प्रदेशको शिक्षाको वर्तमान अवस्थाको मूल्याङ्कन गर्ने ।
- **समावेशी शैक्षिक नीतिहरू विकास गर्न** : शिक्षामा पहुँच, समानता सुनिश्चित गर्दै प्रदेशको अद्वितीय सांस्कृतिक, सामाजिक र आर्थिक सन्दर्भहरूलाई सम्बोधन गर्ने रणनीतिहरू बनाउने ।
- **प्रादेशिक-राष्ट्रिय सहकार्यलाई सुदृढ बनाउन** : प्रादेशिक र राष्ट्रिय सरकारहरू, साथै शैक्षिक संस्थाहरू, नागरिक समाज र निजी क्षेत्रहरू बीचको सहकार्यलाई बढावा दिने
- **शिक्षामा नवप्रवर्तनलाई बढावा दिने** : मधेश का युवा र श्रम बजारका आवश्यकताहरूमा ध्यान केन्द्रित गर्दै पाठ्यक्रम डिजाइन, डिजिटल शिक्षा, र व्यावसायिक शिक्षामा नवीन दृष्टिकोणहरू अन्वेषण गर्दै दिगो विकास प्रति उत्तरदायी मानवपुँजी निर्माणमा टेवा पुर्याउने ।
- **शैक्षिक विकेन्द्रीकरणलाई सहयोग गर्ने** : शिक्षामा प्रादेशिक स्वायत्तता प्रवर्द्धनमा केन्द्रित हुँदै, शैक्षिक नीतिहरूको आकार र कार्यान्वयनमा प्रादेशिक सरकारहरूको भूमिकाबारे छलफल गर्न मञ्च प्रदान गर्ने ।
- **शिक्षक तालिम र व्यावसायिक विकास**: मधेशको सांस्कृतिक र भाषिक विविधताप्रति उत्तरदायी हुने बृहत् शिक्षक तालिम कार्यक्रमहरूको आवश्यकतामा विचारविमर्श गर्ने
- **उच्च शिक्षालाई प्राथमिकता**: मधेश विश्वविद्यालयलाई उच्च शिक्षा र अनुसन्धानमा उत्कृष्टताको केन्द्रको रूपमा स्थापनालाई प्रमुख संस्थाको रूपमा अन्वेषण गर्ने ।
- **कृषि शिक्षामा जोड** : मधेशको कृषि अर्थतन्त्रलाई ध्यानमा राख्दै, सम्मेलनले कृषि शिक्षामा प्रकाश पार्नेछ र दिगो कृषि अभ्यास र ग्रामीण विकासलाई बढावा दिन मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालयको स्थापनालाई प्रमुख संस्थाको रूपमा अन्वेषण गर्ने ।

- **व्यवसायिक शिक्षाको अवस्था:** मधेश प्रदेशवाट सवैभन्दा वढी वैदेशिक रोजगारीमा जानेको संख्या रहेको छ । साथै खुल्ला बोर्डर संस्कृतिक समानताको कारणले बहुसंख्यका विद्यार्थीहरू प्राविधिक शिक्षाको लागि भारत जाने भएकोले प्रदेशमा सम्भाव्य व्यवसायिक शिक्षाको पहिचान भारतीय शिक्षा नीति २०२०को प्रभाव तथा अपनाउनुपर्ने रणनीतिको पहिचान गर्ने ।

मुख्य विषयवस्तुहरू

- **समावेशी शिक्षा:** सीमान्तकृत समुदाय, बालिका शिक्षा, विद्यालय छाडेका र अपाङ्गता भएका व्यक्तिहरूमा केन्द्रित भएर सबैका लागि शिक्षामा पहुँच प्रवर्द्धन गर्ने ।
- **प्रादेशिक शैक्षिक स्वायत्तता:** शिक्षा नीति निर्माण र कार्यान्वयनमा प्रादेशिक सरकारहरूको भूमिकालाई सुदृढ गर्ने ।
- **पाठ्यक्रम विकासमा सांस्कृतिक सान्दर्भिकता:** पाठ्यक्रमले मधेशको सांस्कृतिक र भाषिक विविधता झल्काउने र स्थानीय आवश्यकताहरू लाई सम्बोधन गर्न सामाजिक सिकाई सहितको (Social learning) शिक्षा प्रणाली सुनिश्चित गर्ने ।
- **शिक्षक प्रशिक्षण र विकास :** शिक्षक शिक्षा, व्यावसायिक विकास, र अवधारण सुधार गर्न रणनीति विकास गर्ने ।
- **शिक्षामा प्राविधिक एकीकरण:** स्कूल र विश्वविद्यालयहरूमा डिजिटल शिक्षा, ई-लर्निङ प्लेटफर्महरू, र आईसीटी एकीकरणका लागि अवसरहरू अन्वेषण गर्दै ।
- **व्यावसायिक र प्राविधिक शिक्षा:** विद्यार्थीहरूलाई स्थानीय र विश्वव्यापी रोजगार बजारहरूको लागि आवश्यक सीपहरू प्रदान गर्न व्यावसायिक प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमहरू विस्तार गर्ने ।
- **उच्च शिक्षा र अनुसन्धान :** मधेश विश्वविद्यालयलाई उच्च शिक्षा र अनुसन्धानमा उत्कृष्टताको केन्द्रको रूपमा प्रकाश पार्ने ।
- **एविसिडिईएफ अन्वेषण:** मधेश प्रदेशको शिक्षानीति २०८१ के सवल पक्ष, प्रभावकारी कार्यान्वय, उपयोगिता, चुनौती तथा समाधानको उपाय पहिचान गर्ने ।
- **कृषि शिक्षा र अनुसन्धान:** मधेश प्रदेशको आर्थिक विकासमा कृषि शिक्षा र अनुसन्धानको महत्वलाई प्रकाश पार्ने ।

सम्मेलनको लागि प्रस्तुतीकरणका विषयहरू

- **मधेशको शिक्षा परिदृश्य मूल्याङ्कन**
फोकस: प्रदेशमा वर्तमान शिक्षा स्थिति, सफलताहरू, शैक्षिक मुल्याङ्कनका मापदण्ड विधि तथा प्रकृया, उत्कृष्ट तथा चुनौतीहरूको मूल्याङ्कन ।
- **समावेशी शैक्षिक नीतिहरू**
फोकस: सीमान्तकृत समूहहरूको लागि नीति रणनीतिहरू र शैक्षिक समानता सुधार

- **प्रादेशिक-राष्ट्रीय सहयोग**
फोकस: प्रान्तीय र राष्ट्रिय सरकारहरू, शिक्षाविद्हरू, र निजी क्षेत्रहरू बीचकोसम्बन्ध सुदृढ ।
- **शिक्षामा विकेन्द्रीकरण**
फोकस: विकेन्द्रीकरणले प्रादेशिक सरकारहरूलाई शिक्षामा कसरी सशक्त बनाउनसक्छ भनेर अन्वेषण ।
- **शिक्षक प्रशिक्षण र विकास**
फोकस: मधेशको सांस्कृतिक र भाषिक विविधताप्रति उत्तरदायी बृहत् शिक्षक तालिमका लागि प्रस्तावहरू ।
- **डिजिटल शिक्षा र पाठ्यक्रम डिजाइनमा आविष्कारहरू**
फोकस: मधेशमा प्राविधिक एकीकरण, नवीन पाठ्यक्रम, र व्यावसायिक प्रशिक्षण
- **मधेशमा उच्च शिक्षा**
फोकस: उच्चशिक्षाको भविष्यमा मधेश विश्व विश्वविद्यालयको भूमिका स्थापना गर्ने
- **मधेशको कृषि अर्थतन्त्रको लागि कृषि शिक्षा**
फोकस: कृषि शिक्षाको भविष्यमा मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालयको भूमिका स्थापना गर्ने
- **उन्नत तराई निर्माण**
शिक्षाको माध्यमबाट उत्तरदायिईत्व सहितको नैतिक ब्यक्तित्वको निर्माण गरी स्थानिय स्रोत र साधनमा आधारित उद्योग, उद्यमशिलता, ब्यवसायिक क्षेत्रहरूको पहिचान संग सम्वन्धित विभिन्न सरोकारवालाहरूको समूहलाई संगै ल्याउनेछ।

सरोकारवाला समूहहरू

- **स्थानिय, प्रादेशिक र राष्ट्रिय सरकारका अधिकारीहरू** :राष्ट्रिय, प्रादेशिक र स्थानिय शिक्षा नीतिहरू बीचको पङ्क्तिबद्धताबारे छलफल गर्न ।
- **शैक्षिक विशेषज्ञहरू र शिक्षाविद्हरू**: पाठ्यक्रम विकास, शिक्षाशास्त्र, र शिक्षामा नवीनताको बारेमा ज्ञान साझा गर्न ।
- **नागरिकसमाजसंगठनहरू**:सीमान्तकृतसमुदायहरूकोआवश्यकताहरूकोप्रतिनिधित्व गर्न र समावेशी शिक्षाको वकालत गर्न ।
- **शिक्षक र विद्यालय प्रशासकहरू**: गुणस्तरीय शिक्षा प्रदान गर्न सामना गर्नु पर्ने व्यावहारिक चुनौतीहरूको अन्तरदृष्टि प्रदान गर्न ।
- **निजी क्षेत्रका प्रतिनिधिहरू**: शिक्षामा विशेष गरी प्राविधिक र व्यावसायिक तालिममासार्वजनिक-निजी साझेदारीका लागि अवसरहरू खोज्न ।
- **अन्तर्राष्ट्रिय संस्थाहरू र दातृ निकायहरू**: शैक्षिक विकासलाई सहयोग गर्न र शैक्षिकसुधारमा विश्वव्यापी परिप्रेक्ष्यमा योगदान गर्न ।

अपेक्षित परिणामहरू

- **नीति सिफारिसहरू:**सम्मेलनले मधेशमा शिक्षाको गुणस्तर, समावेशीता र सान्दर्भिकतामा सुधार गर्ने उद्देश्यले प्रदेश र राष्ट्रिय सरकारहरूका लागि ठोस नीति सिफारिसहरू प्रदान गर्नेछ ।
- **सुदृढ सहयोग:** सरकार, शिक्षाविद, नागरिक समाज, र निजी क्षेत्र लगायत विभिन्नसरोकारवालाहरू बीच परिष्कृत सहयोग हुनेछ ।
- **शैक्षिक स्वायत्तताको रूपरेखा:** प्रादेशिक सरकारहरूलाई शिक्षा नीति निर्माणमा थपसक्रिय भूमिका खेल्न सशक्त बनाउनको लागि प्रस्तावित रूपरेखा तयार हुनेछ ।
- **इनोभेसन रोडम्याप :** मधेश प्रदेशको शिक्षा प्रणालीमा प्रविधि र नवीन अभ्यासहरू एकीकृत गर्ने रणनीतिक योजनाको रूपरेखा तयार हुनेछ ।
- **उच्च शिक्षाप्रति प्रतिबद्धता:** मधेश विश्वविद्यालयलाई उच्च शिक्षा र अनुसन्धानमा उत्कृष्टताको केन्द्रको रूपमा स्थापना गर्ने मार्गचित्र प्रस्तुत हुनेछ ।
- **कृषि शिक्षाप्रति प्रतिबद्धता:** मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालयलाई कृषि शिक्षा र अनुसन्धानमा उत्कृष्टताको केन्द्रको रूपमा स्थापना गर्ने मार्गचित्र प्रस्तुत हुनेछ ।

राष्ट्रिय शैक्षिक सम्मेलनले नेपालभरका सरोकारवालाहरू एकजुट भएर मधेश प्रदेश र समग्रराष्ट्रको शिक्षाको भविष्यलाई आकार दिने अनौठो अवसर प्रदान गर्नेछ । समावेशीता, शिक्षण प्रशिक्षण, र शैक्षिक नवप्रवर्तन जस्ता मुख्य मुद्दाहरूलाई सम्बोधन गरेर, सम्मेलनले अझ समतामूलक, सान्दर्भिक र अग्रगामी शिक्षा प्रणाली सिर्जना गर्ने लक्ष्य राखेको छ । यस सहयोगी प्रयासबाट मधेश प्रदेशले आफ्नो क्षेत्रीय पहिचानलाई सम्मान गर्दै राष्ट्रिय विकासमा योगदान गर्दै नेपालको शैक्षिक सुधारमा अग्रणी भूमिका खेल्न अगाडि बढेको छ ।

मा.सतिश कुमार सिंह
Hon.Satish Kumar Singh
मुख्यमन्त्री
Chief Minister

फोन नं. ०११-५२७३०३, ५२३१३३

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शुभकामना मन्तव्य

शिक्षा मानव जीवनको आधारभूत आवश्यकता हो । जसले व्यक्ति, समाज, प्रदेश र राष्ट्रको समुन्नति र समृद्धिमा दूरगामी प्रभाव पार्दछ। समावेशी, व्यवहारिक, गुणस्तरीय र नविन शिक्षाको माध्यमबाट मात्र हामी सशक्त नागरिक निर्माण, सामाजिक रूपान्तरण र दिगो विकासको दिशातर्फ अघि बढ्न सक्छौं।

मधेश प्रदेश सरकारले शिक्षालाई प्रदेश विकासको मेरुदण्डका रूपमा लिई नवीन शैक्षिक सुधार, शिक्षक तालीम, प्राविधिक तथा व्यावसायिक शिक्षा, समावेशी शिक्षाको प्रवर्द्धन, तथा गुणस्तरीय शिक्षा प्रणालीको विकासमा विशेष प्राथमिकता दिई आएको छ। यसै सन्दर्भमा मधेश प्रदेशको शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालयको पहलमा आयोजित राष्ट्रिय शिक्षा सम्मेलनका सन्दर्भमा ज्ञान, अनुभव र विमर्शलाई समेटेर प्रकाशित Abstract पुस्तक एक प्रेरणादायी तथा मार्गदर्शक कृति बन्ने विश्वास लिएको छु।

यस पुस्तकमा सरोकारवालाहरूको बहुमूल्य प्रस्तुति, सुझाव र सिफारिसहरूले निश्चय नै प्रदेश तथा राष्ट्रव्यापी शिक्षाको रूपान्तरणमा महत्वपूर्ण टेवा पुऱ्याउनेछ। शिक्षा क्षेत्रमा क्रियाशील सम्पूर्ण निकायहरू, विज्ञहरू, शिक्षकगण, शिक्षा अभियन्ता र नीति निर्माणकर्ताहरूलाई यो पुस्तक उपयोगी हुनेछ भन्ने पूर्ण विश्वास लिएको छु।

अन्त्यमा, यस महत्वपूर्ण सम्मेलनको सफल आयोजन तथा ज्ञानमूलक पुस्तक प्रकाशनमा संलग्न सम्पूर्ण आयोजक, सहभागी र सम्पादकज्यूहरूलाई वधाई ज्ञापन गर्दछु। पुस्तकका सम्पूर्ण पाठकवृन्दलाई पनि हार्दिक शुभकामना व्यक्त गर्दछु।

सतिश कुमार सिंह

मुख्यमन्त्री

माननीय शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रीज्यूको सन्देश

मधेश प्रदेशको जनकपुरधाममा २०८२, असार १० र ११ (२०२५ जून, २४-२५) मा आयोजना हुन लागेको राष्ट्रिय शिक्षा सम्मेलनमा तपाईं सबैलाई हार्दिक स्वागत गर्दछु। यो सम्मेलन हाम्रो समावेशी, नवप्रवर्तनशील र समानतामूलक शिक्षा प्रणाली निर्माणतर्फको साझा यात्रामा एक महत्वपूर्ण कोसेढुङ्गा हो जसले हाम्रो विविधताले भरिएको समुदायको आकांक्षा र सम्भावनालाई पूर्ण रूपमा प्रतिबिम्बित गर्दछ।

शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालयको जिम्मेवारी पाएको नाताले म मधेश प्रदेश शिक्षा नीति २०८१ मार्फत हामीले लिएका परिवर्तनकारी कदमहरूलाई यहाँ प्रकाश पार्न चाहन्छु। यो नीति शिक्षाविद्, विषयविज्ञ, तथा समुदायका सरोकारवालाहरूको गहिरो र व्यापक परामर्शपछि तयार गरिएको हो। यसले विज्ञान तथा प्रविधिको रूपान्तरण, समुदायको सक्रिय सहभागिता, र व्यवहारिक तथा सीपमूलक शिक्षाको प्रवर्द्धनमार्फत शिक्षा प्रणालीमा गुणस्तर, समानता र समावेशितालाई सुदृढ गर्न प्रतिबद्ध छ।

हामीले सामुदायिक कलेजहरूले स्थानीय विकास, सीपमा आधारित शिक्षा सुनिश्चित गर्न खेलेको महत्वपूर्ण भूमिकालाई स्पष्ट रूपमा पहिचान गरेका छौं। सामुदायिक कलेजहरूले उच्च शिक्षामा पहुँच विस्तार गरेको छ र ग्रामीण तथा पिछडिएका पृष्ठभूमिका विद्यार्थीहरूलाई सशक्त बनाएको छ। यद्यपि, आज ती कलेजहरूले पुरानो पाठ्यक्रम, सीमित स्रोत साधन र प्रविधिको अभावजस्ता चुनौतीहरू भोगिरहेका छन्।

हाम्रो नयाँ नीतिले प्रतिस्पर्धा होइन सहाकार्यमा जोड दिँदै विश्वविद्यालय, सामुदायिक कलेज तथा सबै शैक्षिक संस्था तथा अनुसन्धान केन्द्रहरूको बीचमा सामञ्जस्यताको माध्यमबाट नयाँ नयाँ संस्था निर्माण नगरी वर्तमान शैक्षिक संरचनाको बलियो पक्षलाई उपयोग गर्दै दिगो र समावेशी प्रगतिको मार्ग प्रशस्त गर्नेछ। प्राविधिक तथा व्यावसायिक पाठ्यक्रमहरू, उद्योगसँगको साझेदारी, र डिजिटल शिक्षाको समावेशीकरणले भविष्यका लागि सक्षम जनशक्ति तयार पार्नेछ।

मधेश प्रदेशको सांस्कृतिक विविधता हाम्रो पहिचान हो। यहाँको शिक्षा केवल ज्ञान र सीप आर्जनको माध्यम मात्र होइन, चरित्र निर्माण, एकता प्रवर्द्धन र साझा पहिचान विकास गर्ने महत्वपूर्ण साधन पनि हो। स्थानीय मूल्य, भाषा र परम्परालाई पाठ्यक्रममा समावेश गरेर हामी हाम्रो शिक्षा प्रणालीलाई हाम्रो सांस्कृतिक सम्पदामा आधारित राख्दै विद्यार्थीहरूलाई रोजगार र उद्यमशीलताका लागि तयार पार्दैछौं। यस सांस्कृतिक उत्तरदायी दृष्टिकोणले सामाजिक सद्भाव, नवप्रवर्तन र प्रदेश तथा राष्ट्रको सामाजिक-आर्थिक विकासमा योगदान पुऱ्याउनेछ।

मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालय, मधेश स्वास्थ्य विज्ञान संस्थान, र मधेश विश्वविद्यालयले छोटो समयमै गरेका उल्लेखनीय उपलब्धिहरू र तिनीहरूको समर्पण, मेहनत र योगदानप्रति हृदयदेखि नै सम्मान गर्न चाहन्छु। अनुसन्धान र नवप्रवर्तनको माध्यमबाट शिक्षाको गुणस्तर उकास्ने यी पहलकदमीहरू केवल उपलब्धिहरू मात्र होइनन्, यी त हाम्रो प्रदेशको सुनौलो भविष्य निर्माण गर्ने आधारशीला हुन्। यी सरहानीय कार्यहरूको उच्च मूल्याङ्कन गर्दै मन्त्रालय निरन्तर रूपमा सहयोग गर्न कटिबद्ध रहनेछ।

यस राष्ट्रिय शिक्षा सम्मेलनले हामी सबैलाई गहिरो विचार विमर्श गर्ने र ठोस रणनीति निर्माण गर्ने अवसर प्रदान गर्नेछ। हामीले विगतबाट सिकेका पाठ, वर्तमानका चुनौतीहरू र भविष्यप्रतिको आशालाई सबै मिलेर विश्वविद्यालय र अन्य संस्थाहरूलाई नयाँ उचाइमा पुऱ्याऔं र मधेश प्रदेशका युवाहरूलाई तीव्र परिवर्तनशील विश्वमा सफल हुन योग्य बनाऔं।

अन्तमा म सबै साझेदार, शिक्षक र सहभागीहरूलाई हार्दिक धन्यवाद ज्ञापन गर्दछु। तपाईंहरूको सक्रिय सहभागिता र सुझावहरूले यो सम्मेलन र हाम्रो साझा दृष्टिकोणको सफलतामा महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका खेल्नेछ।

धन्यवाद।

रानी कुमारी तिवारी

माननीय मन्त्री

शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालय

मधेश प्रदेश, नेपाल

Elevating Madhesh Province through Skill School

Madhesh Province stands at a pivotal crossroads in its educational journey. With a vibrant demographic, rich cultural heritage, and a growing appetite for socio-economic advancement, the region has made significant strides in expanding access to education. Yet, persistent challenges—ranging from inadequate infrastructure and teacher shortages to outdated curricula and limited technological integration—continue to impede the realization of its full potential. As the world rapidly transitions into the digital age, the need for a transformative leap in higher education within Madhesh has never been more urgent.

Educational Highlights: Progress and Persistent Gaps

Over the past decade, Madhesh Province has witnessed notable changes in literacy rates, school enrollments, and the establishment of community and private educational institutions. Community engagement, targeted interventions, and government initiatives have begun to address the needs of marginalized groups and promote inclusive education. However, these gains are tempered by persistent gaps in quality, equity, and relevance. The province's youth, brimming with ambition, often migrate beyond borders in search of skilled education and employment—an exodus that underscores the pressing need for homegrown, future-ready educational solutions.

As a resource person in multiple capacity-building programs across Nepal supported by UGC, including curriculum development, academic writing, entrepreneurship, and research publication workshops at Madhesh University, Simra Campus, Gaurishankar Campus, Nijgadh, Public Campus, ChaturbhujeswarJanata Multiple Campus, Janjyoti Multiple Campus, I have taken perception and also learned through visionary leaders of Madhesh during informal discussion and Education Policy development which is expressed here.

The Case for a Skill School under University

In this context, the proposal to establish a full-fledged technological university in Madhesh Province—modeled after the visionary blueprint as Madhesh University is both timely and transformative. Such an institution would not merely be an addition to the educational landscape; it would be a catalyst for holistic societal change, as envisioned by leaders of Madhesh. By integrating technical, vocational, and skill-based education with research and innovation, a technological university would directly address the region's demand for skilled human capital, drive industrial growth, and foster socio-economic resilience.

Innovative Approaches and Strategic Vision

A technological university in Madhesh should embody a “blue ocean” strategy—targeting underserved populations and offering flexible, multi-entry pathways that accommodate both formal and informal learners. The curriculum must be dynamic, continuously updated through research and labor market analysis to anticipate emerging trends and equip students for jobs that

do not yet exist. Interdisciplinary programs spanning engineering, agriculture, health sciences, digital technology, and entrepreneurship will empower graduates to become not just job seekers, but job creators.

The university’s operational model should leverage blended and online learning, virtual campuses, and industry partnerships to maximize reach and impact. Centers of Excellence, community colleges, and skill centers can serve as innovation hubs, fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and government. Credit transfer systems, dual degrees, and lifelong learning opportunities will ensure that education remains accessible, relevant, and adaptable to changing needs.

Socio-Economic Impact and Community Empowerment

Beyond academic excellence, a skill university in Madhesh will serve as an engine for socio-economic transformation. By prioritizing local technology, promoting self-employment, and supporting school dropouts and informal sector workers, the university can help reverse the tide of youth outmigration and foreign employment dependency. Its focus on research, innovation, and entrepreneurship will stimulate local industries, enhance productivity, and contribute to the vision of a “Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepali.”

Call to Action

The journey toward establishing a technological university in Madhesh Province requires collective commitment—of policymakers, educators, industry leaders, and the broader community. The foundation has been laid: land acquisition, infrastructure planning, and curriculum development are underway, and the draft for including Skill school under the provision of Madhesh University Act based on Madhesh Province Education Policy 2081 is with the relevant authorities. Now is the time for intellectual, financial, and moral support to bring this vision to fruition by collaborating with existing community colleges.

Education is the cornerstone of societal progress, and in the era of technological disruption and globalization, Madhesh Province must seize the opportunity to redefine its educational paradigm. By launching a world-class technological university, the province can set a new benchmark for innovation, inclusivity, and economic empowerment—not only for its youth but for the entire nation.

Let us unite to build an institution that not only imparts knowledge but also shapes character, fosters creativity, and drives the prosperity of Madhesh and Nepal. The future demands it, and together, we can make history by implementing Madhesh Province Education Policy 2081.

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Member

Province Policy and Planning Commission

Madhesh Province

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Strengthening Local Education Governance through Evidence-Based Planning and Accountability

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Abstract

Nepal's shift to federalism mandates local governments to ensure inclusive and quality education through context-specific plans that prioritize marginalized groups, including girls, children with disabilities, youth, and disadvantaged communities. These plans must align with the national School Education Sector Plan (SESP) 2022–2032 and international commitments such as Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). However, many local governments face resource constraints, limited technical capacity, and budgetary challenges, which hinder effective education planning, implementation, and monitoring. Consequently, educational inequities persist, particularly for vulnerable populations.

To address these challenges, this study introduces the Local Education Plan Analysis Framework (LEAF), a participatory toolkit designed to strengthen education governance at the local level. LEAF enables civil society organizations (CSOs), education advocates, and local stakeholders to critically assess education plans, ensuring alignment with equity goals, learning outcomes, and SDG 4 indicators. The framework facilitates evidence-based planning by benchmarking local plans against national and international standards, promoting accountability through citizen engagement, and building local capacity for participatory decision-making.

LEAF's key contributions include: Evidence-Based Planning: Structured analysis of local education plans to identify gaps and opportunities for marginalized groups, supporting data-driven policy improvements. Accountability and Engagement: Empowering CSOs and communities to monitor policy implementation, amplify marginalized voices, and hold duty-bearers accountable for equitable education outcomes. Capacity Building: Enhancing technical skills and fostering participatory governance to ensure education plans reflect local needs and priorities.

By bridging policy formulation and grassroots implementation, LEAF fosters sustainable, equitable, and locally owned education systems in Nepal. This framework offers a practical approach to operationalizing constitutional mandates and international commitments, advancing Nepal's progress toward achieving inclusive and quality education for all.

Keywords: evidence-based planning, accountability, local ownership, education governance, SDG 4, inclusive education, federalism, policy alignment.

Innovative Approaches to Teaching and Learning: A Transformative Path in Health and Nursing Education

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Abstract

In the context of rapidly evolving educational demands, the adoption of innovative teaching and learning strategies is critical to preparing health and nursing professionals for complex, real-world challenges. This paper examines transformative educational methodologies within health and nursing education, emphasizing experiential, learner-centered, and technology-integrated approaches. Drawing on both academic literature and field-based experience, the study explores the effectiveness of problem-based learning (PBL), simulation-based training, inter-professional collaboration, and the integration of digital tools in fostering critical thinking, clinical reasoning, and compassionate care among students. These methodologies are positioned not merely as technological advancements but as comprehensive pedagogical shifts that empower educators and learners alike.

The analysis underscores the necessity of contextualizing educational innovation within the socio-cultural realities of Madhesh Province and the broader Nepali health system. It highlights that meaningful innovation extends beyond the adoption of new technologies to include reflective practice, community engagement, and the creation of inclusive learning environments. By aligning educational strategies with local needs and values, these approaches contribute to the development of a responsive and resilient health workforce capable of addressing both current and emerging health challenges.

Furthermore, the paper advocates for institutional and policy-level support to sustain such innovations, urging educators, policymakers, and institutional leaders to reimagine teaching and learning frameworks. Emphasis is placed on ensuring that educational reforms are inclusive, future-oriented, and aligned with provincial and national visions for quality education and health service delivery. Ultimately, the integration of innovative, context-sensitive educational practices is presented as a pathway to strengthening the capacity, adaptability, and compassion of Nepal's health workforce.

Keywords: Innovation, Health System, Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Simulation-Based Training, Inter-Professional Collaboration

Strengthening Education through Community Engagement and Partnerships

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Abstract

Sustainable and inclusive educational transformation fundamentally depends on the active participation of communities and the establishment of robust local partnerships. This paper examines the pivotal role of community engagement and multi-sectoral collaboration in advancing educational access, equity, and quality, with particular focus on marginalized and rural regions of Madhesh Province. Drawing on the grassroots activism of Author involved as axiology, the study presents lived experiences and case examples illustrating how community-driven initiatives have successfully reduced dropout rates, enhanced girls' education, supported children from Dalit and marginalized backgrounds, and fostered a culture of accountability within local schools. These initiatives demonstrate that when communities are empowered to take ownership of educational processes, they can effectively address entrenched barriers related to poverty, discrimination, and social exclusion.

The analysis underscores the transformative potential of meaningful partnerships among schools, parents, civil society organizations, and local governments. Such collaborations are essential for dismantling structural impediments to education and for ensuring that interventions are contextually relevant and sustainable. The paper further emphasizes the importance of culturally sensitive and locally owned strategies that respect and incorporate the knowledge, language, and traditions of Madheshi communities, thereby promoting greater inclusivity and relevance in educational programming.

Additionally, the session advocates for the development of institutional mechanisms that facilitate inclusive dialogue, shared responsibility, and participatory decision-making in education governance. By fostering collective ownership and community empowerment, these mechanisms can transform the education system in Madhesh Province into a catalyst for social justice and sustainable development. The findings suggest that educational reforms rooted in community engagement not only improve educational outcomes but also contribute to broader goals of equity and social transformation.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Institutional Mechanism, Social Justice, Sustainable Development

Driving Educational Excellence through Digital Transformation

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Abstract

Digital transformation in education transcends the mere integration of technology; it involves fundamentally reimagining how learning is designed, delivered, and experienced. This paper explores the transformative potential of digital tools and platforms in enhancing teaching and learning processes, promoting inclusivity, and bridging educational disparities, particularly in regions such as Madhesh Province, Nepal. Amidst the global acceleration of digital adoption, Nepal's education sector is presented with unprecedented opportunities to innovate through online learning platforms, virtual classrooms, artificial intelligence-powered educational tools, and data-driven decision-making.

Drawing on practical models and scalable strategies, this study highlights approaches that align with Madhesh Province's vision for equitable and future-ready education. Emphasis is placed on locally adaptable solutions, including open-source technologies, offline digital content, mobile learning, and community-based digital literacy programs, which are critical in contexts with limited connectivity and infrastructure. These solutions not only enhance accessibility but also empower learners and educators by providing flexible, context-sensitive educational resources.

The paper also addresses significant challenges impeding digital transformation, such as inadequate digital infrastructure, limited teacher readiness, cybersecurity concerns, and persistent access disparities affecting rural and marginalized students. It advocates for a collaborative, multi-stakeholder approach involving government agencies, educators, technology experts, and local communities to develop a resilient digital ecosystem that supports continuous and inclusive learning.

By investing strategically in digital capacity building and inclusive policy frameworks, Madhesh Province can spearhead a bold and sustainable educational transformation. This research aims to inspire policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to embrace digital innovation with a commitment to equity, ensuring that technological advancements translate into meaningful educational outcomes for all learners.

Keywords: digital transformation, teaching-learning processes, open-source technologies, inclusive education, educational equity

Challenges and Opportunities in Madhesh Province

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Abstract

Madhesh Province, characterized by its rich cultural heritage and demographic diversity, is at a pivotal moment in advancing inclusive and transformative educational reform. This paper examines the multifaceted challenges and opportunities influencing the province's education system within the broader context of decentralization, social equity, and capacity development. Key challenges identified include inadequate infrastructure in rural and marginalized communities, persistent gender and caste-based disparities, a shortage of qualified teachers, weak policy implementation, and the absence of a localized curriculum that authentically reflects the linguistic and cultural identity of Madheshi society. These challenges are exacerbated by political instability and limited coordination among agencies, which undermine consistent policy enforcement and institutional accountability.

Despite these obstacles, Madhesh Province holds significant potential to redefine its educational landscape. The transition to provincial autonomy offers an unprecedented opportunity for locally grounded educational planning, enabling policies that are more responsive to community needs and aspirations. Strategic opportunities include leveraging local languages and indigenous knowledge systems, fostering public-private partnerships, investing in digital education infrastructure, and enhancing teacher capacity through sustained professional development. Furthermore, the province's youthful population represents a dynamic resource for innovation and civic engagement, which can be mobilized to reimagine education as a vehicle for equity, inclusion, and cultural pride.

This study advocates for a collaborative approach that embraces innovation and community ownership to build a responsive, equitable, and culturally relevant education system in Madhesh Province. By addressing structural barriers and capitalizing on local strengths, the province can bridge educational gaps and promote social justice. This session aims to stimulate critical dialogue on pathways toward sustainable educational transformation that honors Madhesh's unique socio-cultural context.

Keywords: caste-based disparities, teacher capacity, educational equity, decentralization, cultural inclusion, community ownership

Innovative approaches of Madhesh University

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Abstract

Madhesh University (MU), established in 2022, is emerging as a pioneering institution driving educational innovation and socio-economic development in Nepal's Madhesh Province. Adopting a blue ocean competitive strategy, MU targets underserved populations through innovative educational models that blend traditional knowledge with modern technology and skill development. The university emphasizes interdisciplinary research, applied learning, and community engagement to address local challenges such as sustainable agriculture, health, and governance.

Key initiatives include the Institute of Federalism, the Unnath Tarai Abhiyan through dialogue series on critical issues and community development project, and a School Adoption Program aimed at improving educational outcomes and infrastructure in local schools. MU integrates digital education and data-driven pedagogies to foster learner engagement and enhance teaching quality. A notable achievement is the university's patent application for a technology-driven risk management solution, underscoring its commitment to leveraging technology for practical societal impact.

MU's strategic focus on establishing Centers of Excellence in critical fields, fostering industry collaborations, and promoting entrepreneurship education supports regional economic growth and innovation. The university's environmental stewardship is reflected in programs like "Plant a Tree for Graduation" and collaborative research on sustainability, positioning MU as a leader in ecological preservation alongside academic excellence.

By combining academic rigor, technological advancement, and community-centered initiatives, Madhesh University is transforming higher education in the region. Its efforts to harness the demographic dividend, empower marginalized communities, and build institutional capacity align with Nepal's broader development goals. MU's innovative approaches create a dynamic learning ecosystem that prepares students for global challenges while contributing to the prosperity and resilience of Madhesh Province.

Keywords: Madhesh University, educational innovation, community engagement, interdisciplinary research, digital education, sustainable development

Perception of Health Worker on Integration of Nursing Education and Nursing Services at Provincial Hospital, Janakpurdham

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Abstract

Integration between nursing education and nursing services remains a critical challenge in healthcare, yet it is essential for enhancing patient care, ensuring emotional safety, reducing workload, and fostering effective interdisciplinary communication. Bridging the gap between nursing education and clinical practice is vital for improving healthcare outcomes. This study aimed to assess the perceptions of health workers regarding the integration of nursing education and nursing services.

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 158 health workers at Provincial Hospital, Janakpurdham, Nepal. The sample comprised 46 staff nurses, 32 consultant doctors, 28 medical doctors, 23 auxiliary nurse midwives (ANMs), and 26 nursing and medical teaching staff, selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire based on a three-point Likert scale to evaluate healthcare providers' perceptions of nursing education-service integration. Descriptive statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.

Findings revealed that 74.5% of participants held a high perception of integration between nursing education and services, 18% had a medium perception, and 7.5% reported a low perception. Notably, doctors and teaching faculty exhibited higher perceptions of integration compared to nursing staff, who generally demonstrated moderate perceptions.

Overall, health workers exhibited a predominantly positive perception of the integration between nursing education and nursing services. Male participants and teaching faculty members demonstrated significantly higher perceptions than their female and non-teaching counterparts. These findings underscore the importance of fostering stronger collaboration between educational and clinical nursing sectors to enhance healthcare delivery.

Keywords: Health Worker, Integration, Nursing Education, Nursing Services

Factors affecting Professional Development of Teachers of Secondary Schools in Nepal

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Abstract

This paper synthesizes existing literature to identify key factors influencing the professional development of secondary school teachers in Nepal. It examines personal, environmental, and academic components, with particular attention to digital literacy, and how these elements collectively impact teacher growth. The study also considers the role of student-related factors in shaping educational and professional progress. Findings highlight that both monetary incentives—such as salary, allowances, and insurance—and non-monetary incentives—including promotion opportunities, training, field visits, and participation in international conferences—significantly motivate teachers' professional development. Financial incentives enhance teachers' well-being and attractiveness to professional growth, while non-monetary rewards foster sustained engagement, collaborative learning cultures, job satisfaction, and a sense of accomplishment.

Environmental factors such as school infrastructure, class size, workload, and availability of teaching materials also critically affect teachers' capacity for professional growth. The study emphasizes the importance of organizational support and teacher engagement as synergistic components that sustain professional development. However, challenges persist, including inadequate implementation of acquired knowledge in classrooms, limited financial resources for development programs, and disparities between community and institutional schools in access to professional development opportunities.

Moreover, the research underscores the need for localized, context-sensitive training programs that address the specific needs of Nepalese secondary school teachers. It advocates for decentralized teacher training to overcome geographic and systemic barriers, and for institutionalizing participatory practices within schools to enhance organizational support. Continuous professional development is recognized as vital for equipping teachers with pedagogical, content, and contextual knowledge necessary to meet 21st-century educational demands.

This comprehensive review informs policymakers, educators, and stakeholders about effective strategies and persistent challenges in teacher professional development, providing a foundation for designing targeted interventions to improve the quality of secondary education in Nepal.

Keywords: professional development, personal factors, environmental factors, digital literacy, teacher growth, secondary education, Nepal

Educational Reform for Creative and Healthy Mind

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Abstract

A healthy society—characterized by peace, prosperity, and minimal corruption—depends fundamentally on the qualities instilled in children through education. Echoing Nelson Mandela’s assertion that “education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world,” this paper critically examines the current state of education and its role in shaping societal well-being. Contemporary teaching practices often undermine creativity by emphasizing passive learning and overwhelming students with excessive content, thereby stifling critical thinking and active engagement. Such an approach not only diminishes individual potential but also weakens the social fabric by neglecting core values essential for a just and moral society.

True education, as Albert Einstein emphasized, is not the mere acquisition of facts but the cultivation of the mind’s capacity to think independently and creatively. Addressing societal issues like corruption requires more than legal reforms; it demands a transformation of individual morality. Passive transmission of moral facts is insufficient—moral values must be deeply ingrained through reflective practice and the encouragement of insightful wisdom that enables students to discern right from wrong autonomously. The Reference Book on Comparative Assessment from the Eastern approach feel there is a need to move towards a new symbiosis of Western Enlighten and Eastern Awakening to create a new path of development for producing total quality people.

This paper advocates for a radical reform of the education system that integrates scientific and technological knowledge with spiritual and social values. Nepal’s rich spiritual heritage offers a unique foundation for nurturing healthy minds capable of contributing to a healthy society. Curriculum designers and educational stakeholders must therefore prioritize the creation of learning environments that promote active, goal-directed learning while embedding ethical and spiritual dimensions. Such an integrative approach can foster creativity, moral integrity, and social responsibility, ultimately steering society toward sustainable peace and prosperity.

Keywords: educational reform, active learning, goal-directed learning, spirituality in education, moral development, creativity

Educational Sacrifice of Youth: Shouldering Intergenerational Responsibilities

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Abstract

This study investigates the complex motivations and lived experiences of Nepali youth who opt for labor migration instead of pursuing higher education. While prior quantitative research has identified social, cultural, economic, educational, and kinship factors influencing youth migration decisions, this qualitative inquiry provides deeper insights through personal narratives. Drawing on 22 in-depth interviews with youth labor returnees and local key informants, the research explores how young individuals interpret and negotiate these influencing factors within their socio-economic contexts.

The findings reveal that many youths abandon higher education due to familial obligations, economic hardship, and limited local employment opportunities. Migration is frequently perceived as a necessary strategy to support family members, finance siblings' education, arrange sisters' marriages, and elevate household social status. Thematic analysis, conducted using Atlas.ti software, identified five core themes: Accountability to Family, Economic Support, Completing Family Responsibility, Skill Acquisition, and Social Status. These themes highlight the centrality of intergenerational responsibility and a sense of educational futility in shaping migration choices.

This study underscores the tension between educational aspirations and economic imperatives faced by Nepali youth, emphasizing how short-term financial needs often compel them to sacrifice long-term educational goals. The narratives suggest that existing policies inadequately address this dilemma, calling for more nuanced interventions that reconcile educational access with economic realities. By fostering opportunities that integrate skill development, economic support, and educational advancement, policymakers can better support youth in balancing family responsibilities with personal growth.

Overall, the research contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of youth migration in Nepal, advocating for policy frameworks that mitigate educational sacrifice and promote sustainable socio-economic development.

Keywords: youth migration, intergenerational responsibility, educational sacrifice, labor returnees, family obligation

The Need of Clinical (Learning by Doing) Approach in School Education: A Comprehensive Analysis

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Abstract

Education serves as the foundational pillar of a nation, shaping the future by influencing individual behavior and personality development. The quality of education a child receives fundamentally determines their potential and, by extension, the strength of the nation's social and economic fabric. Particularly, primary education forms the critical base upon which the entire educational structure rests; thus, strengthening school-level education is essential for building a resilient nation. This article critically examines the urgent need to integrate the clinical approach to learning—a student-centered, experiential pedagogy grounded in “learning by doing”—into existing school curricula and teaching methodologies.

The clinical approach fosters the development of essential life skills and practical understanding from an early age, promoting active engagement and critical thinking among students. By exploring the core principles and diverse facets of clinical education, this study highlights its potential benefits, including enhanced learner autonomy, improved problem-solving abilities, and deeper conceptual comprehension. Additionally, the article addresses potential challenges in implementing this approach, such as resource constraints, teacher preparedness, and curriculum adaptation.

Finally, the article proposes strategic recommendations for educational reform aimed at facilitating a paradigm shift toward clinical learning. These include capacity building for educators, curriculum redesign to incorporate experiential learning components, and policy support to institutionalize the approach. By adopting the clinical approach, educational systems can transform passive learners into active, reflective individuals—turning ‘naive kids’ into ‘wise adults’ capable of contributing meaningfully to society.

Keywords: clinical approach, experiential learning, primary education, student-centered pedagogy, educational reform

Enhancing Safety Climate through Occupational Safety and Health Training in the Healthcare Setting: The mediating Role of Safety Communication

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) training on the safety climate within healthcare settings, emphasizing the mediating role of OSH communication. Healthcare workers are exposed to numerous occupational risks, making effective OSH strategies crucial for fostering a positive safety culture. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 250 healthcare professionals—including doctors, nurses, and technical staff—via a structured questionnaire assessing perceptions of OSH training, OSH communication, and safety climate. The relationships among these variables were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software to conduct impact, correlation, and mediation analyses.

Findings indicate that OSH training has a significant direct positive effect on both OSH communication ($\beta = 0.54$) and safety climate ($\beta = 0.52$). Additionally, OSH communication positively influences safety climate ($\beta = 0.25$). Mediation analysis reveals that OSH communication partially mediates the relationship between OSH training and safety climate, suggesting that the effectiveness of training is enhanced when accompanied by clear, consistent communication regarding safety issues within the organizational context.

These results underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive OSH training programs with strategic communication initiatives to cultivate a favorable safety climate in healthcare environments. The dual influence of training and communication offers practical implications for hospital administrators aiming to improve safety culture and reduce occupational hazards. By prioritizing both components, healthcare institutions can strengthen their capacity to protect workers and enhance overall organizational safety performance.

Keywords: healthcare setting, mediation analysis, occupational safety and health, safety climate, structural equation modeling (SEM)

Education Policy and Governance

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Abstract

Education policy and governance are critical foundations for establishing an equitable, inclusive, and high-quality education system. Within Nepal's federal structure, provincial governments possess the authority to design and implement education policies tailored to the socio-cultural, economic, and linguistic contexts of their populations. Madhesh Province, characterized by its rich diversity and distinct challenges, necessitates a governance framework that is responsive, accountable, and grounded in local realities.

This National Education Conference aims to critically assess the current state of education policy and governance across federal, provincial, and local levels in Nepal. It serves as a collaborative platform for policymakers, educators, researchers, and civil society actors to identify existing policy gaps, implementation barriers, and opportunities for reform. The conference emphasizes the alignment of provincial education policies with constitutional mandates, the promotion of participatory and inclusive planning processes, and the enhancement of efficient service delivery mechanisms.

Key thematic areas include intergovernmental coordination, curriculum contextualization to reflect local needs, teacher recruitment and management strategies, sustainable financing mechanisms, digital transformation in education, and active community participation. Particular focus is placed on ensuring equitable access for marginalized groups such as Dalits, girls, children with disabilities, and linguistic minorities, thereby addressing systemic disparities.

The conference endeavors to generate actionable recommendations aimed at strengthening education governance through decentralized authority, evidence-based policymaking, and robust accountability systems. By fostering dialogue and shared learning, it seeks to contribute to the formulation of a resilient, inclusive, and forward-looking education policy framework for Madhesh Province. Ultimately, this framework aspires to uphold the constitutional right to quality education for all citizens, thereby supporting sustainable social and economic development.

Keywords: education policy, quality education, intergovernmental coordination, financing mechanisms, inclusive governance

Strengthening the Universities of Madhesh Province, Nepal

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Abstract

Universities in Madhesh Province possess significant potential to catalyze regional development, foster innovation, and promote social equity. However, these institutions currently face multiple challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, limited academic autonomy, insufficient research funding, faculty shortages, and weak linkages between academia and industry. Addressing these issues requires a strategic, multidimensional approach that aligns higher education with provincial needs, local aspirations, and global standards.

This paper identifies key interventions essential for revitalizing higher education in Madhesh Province. These include strengthening institutional governance and safeguarding academic freedom, ensuring equitable resource distribution, promoting inclusive access for marginalized communities, investing in research and innovation, and developing curricula that are responsive to industry demands. The role of provincial autonomy in higher education policymaking is emphasized as a means to enable universities to reflect Madhesh's unique socio-cultural identity and development priorities.

The paper also highlights the importance of establishing and upgrading specialized universities in fields such as agriculture, technology, and health sciences to address local challenges and cultivate skilled human capital. Enhancing teacher training programs, expanding digital infrastructure, and fostering international collaborations are further identified as critical pathways to improving educational quality and relevance.

Ultimately, this study argues that empowering universities in Madhesh Province transcends academic reform; it constitutes a broader strategy for sustainable development, social justice, and provincial legitimacy. A robust and inclusive university system can serve as a cornerstone for transformative change in Madhesh and exemplify effective decentralized higher education governance within Nepal.

Keywords: regional development, academic freedom, industry-relevant curricula, international collaboration, higher education governance

Twenty Years of the Madhesh Movement: Minor Improvement in Education, no Uplift in the People's Level of Education-“Current Situation, Opportunities, Challenges, and Way Forward for Madhesh Province’s Education System”

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Abstract

Madhesh Province, despite its cultural and economic importance, faces severe educational disparities compared to other provinces in Nepal. With a literacy rate of approximately 64%, the lowest nationwide, and significant gender gaps—72% male literacy versus 55% female literacy—the province struggles with systemic inequities rooted in poverty, caste discrimination, and inadequate educational infrastructure. Nationally, Nepal’s literacy rate stands at 76.2%, highlighting Madhesh’s lag due to chronic underfunding, with only 6% of its provincial budget allocated to education, alongside teacher shortages and political interference in school management. Human development indicators further underscore these challenges, with Madhesh ranking lowest among Nepal’s seven provinces in both the Human Development Index (0.51) and Gender Development Index (0.929).

Historically, Madhesh was a fertile ground for education, producing notable educators who contributed significantly to Nepal’s educational landscape. However, recent trends reveal a decline, with many families compelled to send their children to schools outside the province and a growing reliance on labor migration. Approximately 14% of children in Madhesh have never attended school, and dropout rates remain alarmingly high, particularly in community schools. The province also experiences a disproportionate share of children engaged in income-generating activities, which further hampers educational attainment.

These persistent disparities pose significant challenges to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims for inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Despite some progress, Madhesh’s educational indicators continue to lag behind national averages, threatening the principle of Leave No One Behind (LNOB) central to the SDGs. Addressing these issues requires concerted efforts to improve infrastructure, teacher quality, governance, and equitable resource allocation, alongside targeted interventions to overcome socio-economic and cultural barriers.

Keywords: poverty, caste discrimination, inadequate infrastructure, Sustainable Development Goals, Leave No One Behind, educational disparities

Innovative Approaches to Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

This research explores innovative approaches to the teaching and learning process, emphasizing their role in delivering effective and relevant education. Proper education encompasses holistic development, foundational learning, relevance, inclusivity, accessibility, values, citizenship, qualified instruction, and effective methodologies. Teaching is defined as the structured transfer of knowledge and skills from teacher to learner, while learning is a dynamic, continuous process influenced by experiences, social interactions, and environmental contexts. Understanding complex learning theories enhances both educational practice and personal growth.

Innovative teaching approaches aim to improve learning outcomes by employing engaging, interactive, and student-centered methods, often leveraging technology. These approaches include personalized learning, project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, flipped classrooms, gamification, collaborative learning, experiential learning, technology integration, blended learning, visual-based learning, role-playing, and the Jigsaw method. Such methods create more engaging, effective, and contextually relevant learning experiences for students across diverse ages and backgrounds.

The evolution of teaching approaches reflects broader scientific and technological advancements, necessitating that educators remain vigilant and adaptable in their pedagogical strategies. Without a thorough understanding of contemporary teaching methods, educators may struggle to succeed in the classroom. Therefore, continuous professional development and the integration of innovative techniques are essential for fostering effective teaching and meaningful learning in today's rapidly changing educational landscape.

Keywords: holistic development, inclusive education, technology integration, student-centered learning, innovative teaching methods

Inclusive and Equitable Education

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Abstract

Inclusive education aims to ensure that all children, regardless of background or ability, receive quality learning in supportive environments. However, in Nepal's Madhesh Province, significant barriers impede this goal. Challenges include inadequate teacher training, irregular student attendance, and limited use of student-centered methodologies. Overcrowded classrooms, poor infrastructure, and unsafe learning conditions exacerbate disparities. Social norms, gender biases, peer violence, and discrimination against children with disabilities further hinder inclusion. Additionally, inactive School Management Committees (SMCs) and political interference often obstruct effective policy implementation, neglecting marginalized students' needs.

Educational assessments such as NASA, NARN, and EGRA reveal critical learning deficiencies: grade 3 students correctly solve only 43.5% of reading and 37.2% of numeracy problems, with just 20% of children in grades 2–3 possessing foundational literacy and numeracy skills. Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) enrollment is insufficient, with only 62.9% of grade 1 entrants in Madhesh having ECCD experience, below the national average of 76.7%. Promotion rates are particularly low among marginalized groups, including Dalits and Muslims.

To address these challenges, World Vision International Nepal's SIKAI Project in Sarlahi district prioritizes equitable education for vulnerable children. The project integrates child-centered teaching, inclusive pedagogy, and supplementary learning materials while improving school infrastructure, including Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) facilities. Assistive devices such as glasses, rollators, CP chairs, and hearing aids have been provided to 289 children with disabilities, enhancing their educational access. Furthermore, 600 out-of-school children received educational materials to facilitate their transition into formal schooling.

Sustainable policy reforms and collaborative efforts among government, communities, and development partners remain essential to ensure that no child is left behind and that inclusive education becomes a reality in Madhesh Province.

Keywords: inclusive education, marginalized groups, child-centered teaching, formal schooling, educational equity

Addressing Gaps in Inclusive and Equitable Education for Marginalized and Children with Disability in Madhesh Province

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Abstract

Nepal's commitment to inclusive and equitable education is firmly embedded in key policies, including the Constitution of Nepal (2015), the Inclusive Education Policy (2017), the National Education Policy (2019), the School Education Sector Plan (2022–2030), and the Madhesh Province Education Policy (2024). These frameworks guarantee compulsory and free education up to the basic level and free secondary education, explicitly including children with disabilities (CwD), in alignment with the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD). Despite the Ministry of Education and Culture's endorsement of multiple education-related policies and guidelines, significant implementation gaps persist due to budgetary constraints and limited technical human resources. A 2018 Human Rights Watch report highlights persistent barriers faced by CwD in accessing quality education, underscoring the urgency for targeted interventions.

In response, People in Need (PIN), through its EU-funded ACCESS project, conducted a qualitative assessment in 2024 across nine schools in Madhesh Province. The study found that community schools lack inclusive infrastructure—such as ramps, accessible toilets, and assistive devices—alongside inclusive curricular materials and trained resource teachers. These deficiencies contribute to higher dropout rates and irregular attendance among marginalized students and CwD. PIN is actively strengthening local Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) to advocate for inclusive education and equitable access for marginalized children.

To advance inclusive education, the Ministry of Education and Culture should endorse and operationalize the School Education Sector Plan aligned with national guidelines, providing technical and financial support to local governments for developing Local Education Plans (LEPs). Expanding inclusive education programs, enhancing monitoring frameworks, and increasing scholarships for CwD and marginalized groups are critical. Furthermore, teacher training and the establishment of Community Learning Centers focused on inclusive education, coupled with community engagement and CSO capacity building, will improve access and quality.

Sustained policy reforms and collaborative efforts are essential to realize inclusive and equitable education for all children in Nepal.

Keywords: inclusive education, equitable education, children with disabilities, policy implementation, Madhesh Province

Strengthening School Governance: A Review of School Management Committees in Nepal

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Abstract

In Nepal, School Management Committees (SMCs) govern public schools. This article examines the effectiveness of the SMCs. Participatory governance units like SMCs ensure accountability, openness, and community involvement in public school management. National law requires public schools to have a nine-member School Management Committee with a minimum of three female members and led by community-elected parents; however, implementation often deviates.

The study examines SMCs' performance, issues, and impact on public school education. This study synthesizes educational policy, research, publications, and media sources using a desk review method. SMCs are responsible for developing, implementing, and overseeing the School Improvement Plan (SIP) under the Education Act 2001 (amendment), which they monitor and evaluate.

School Management Committees (SMCs) ensure that school activities meet national curriculum, rules, and performance standards while meeting student, parent, and community needs. The study results reveal that capacity, awareness, political intervention, and stakeholder participation limit the effectiveness of many SMCs. SMCs in Madhesh Province are often inactive or just managed in documents in comparison to other provinces. This province has the most out-of-school children (20%) and the lowest literacy rate (85.7%), unlike Gandaki Province, which excels in all categories. Youth employment remains a challenge, with 13.5% of the nation working. The research shows that effective SMCs can improve governance, accountability, and educational equity. However, poor execution, political interference, and empowerment limit their efficacy.

Institutional adjustments, capacity development, and inclusive stakeholder involvement are needed to improve School Management Committees and provide effective and equitable public education in Nepal, especially in unequal areas.

Keywords: School Management Committees (SMCs), Governance, Community Engagement, Education Equity

Mapping the Educational Landscape of Madhesh Province: Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract

This paper, "Mapping the Educational Landscape of Madhesh Province: Challenges and Prospects," provides a comprehensive analysis of the current state of education in Madhesh Province, Nepal. Despite progress in expanding access—particularly at the primary level—the province continues to lag behind national averages in literacy and enrollment, with pronounced disparities affecting girls and marginalized groups. Literacy rates in Madhesh stand at approximately 55.6%, with significant gender and regional gaps. Early childhood education participation and foundational learning outcomes remain low, with only about 25% of early grade students demonstrating basic literacy and numeracy skills. The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated these challenges, causing learning losses and increased dropout rates, especially among girls aged 10–17.

Public schools in Madhesh face critical infrastructure deficits, including inadequate classrooms, sanitation facilities, and teaching materials, particularly in rural areas. High student-teacher ratios, untrained educators, and reliance on rote learning methods undermine educational quality. Governance issues, political interference, and weak oversight further hinder accountability and improvements. While higher education is expanding, it remains underdeveloped, with outdated curricula, limited research capacity, and faculty shortages contributing to brain drain as many students migrate to urban centers or abroad.

Government initiatives such as the Free and Compulsory Education Act and decentralization under federalism offer potential but require enhanced coordination, funding, and capacity-building. The paper recommends targeted investments in infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum reform, and inclusive education policies, with particular focus on marginalized populations, girls, and children with disabilities.

In conclusion, while Madhesh Province has made strides in educational access, significant challenges in quality and equity persist. Addressing these requires sustained, inclusive, and collaborative efforts among government, communities, and development partners to transform education and promote equitable learning outcomes.

Keywords: educational landscape, foundational learning, political interference, educational transformation, Madhesh Province

Challenges and Opportunities in Madhesh Province in Education

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Abstract

This abstract presents an overview of the education sector in Madhesh Province, Nepal, highlighting key statistics, challenges, and opportunities related to schools, students, and teachers. Madhesh Province, with a dense population of over 6 million people within 9,661 sq.km, hosts 3,286 community schools serving approximately 1.2 million students, supported by 20,229 teachers. However, the student-teacher ratio stands at an alarming 60:1, far exceeding the standards prescribed by the current Education Act. Moreover, teacher deployment is uneven, with many schools lacking adequate staffing relative to student numbers (UN Nepal Platform, EMIS 2021-22).

Net enrollment rates vary across educational levels: 96.9% for grades 1–5, 93.3% for grades 6–8, and a sharp decline to 56% for secondary education (grades 9–12). Despite high enrollment in early grades, dropout rates remain a significant concern, with about 5.5% of students leaving school prematurely, often to seek employment. The dropout issue is compounded by poor school infrastructure, insufficient teaching materials, and a lack of teacher training in modern pedagogical methods. Many students from low-income families attend community schools, where educational quality is often compromised. A poignant reflection of this challenge is the common sentiment among students anticipating migration abroad for work rather than pursuing further education.

Quality education remains the most pressing challenge in Madhesh Province. Schools are inadequately equipped, and teachers frequently lack timely training in new technologies and teaching methods. Despite students spending up to 12 years in school, many do not acquire essential life skills or secure promising futures.

In conclusion, Madhesh Province faces critical challenges in student-teacher ratios, enrollment, dropout rates, and educational quality. Addressing these issues requires coordinated efforts to improve teacher deployment, infrastructure, pedagogical training, and student retention strategies to ensure meaningful learning outcomes and future opportunities for all students.

Keywords: student-teacher ratio, net enrollment, dropout, quality education, Madhesh province

Improvements of Medical Education through Problem-based Learning (PBL) in Madhesh Province, Nepal

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Abstract

This paper addresses the urgent need to reform medical education in Madhesh Province, Nepal, where conventional, lecture-based teaching predominates, often neglecting clinical reasoning, problem-solving, and community relevance. The province faces a complex health burden, including high maternal mortality, infectious diseases, and rising non-communicable diseases, which current curricula inadequately prepare students to address, especially in rural and underserved areas. This disconnect results in a healthcare workforce that is theoretically knowledgeable but lacks practical, community-focused competencies.

The proposed project seeks funding to develop, implement, and evaluate a structured Problem-Based Learning (PBL) module within the undergraduate medical curriculum across multiple medical schools in Madhesh Province. The initiative aims to enhance faculty capacity through training in collaborative and experiential learning facilitation, develop locally relevant case-based modules aligned with regional health concerns, and institutionalize formal PBL tutorials. Students will engage in independent research, define learning objectives, and participate in problem-solving discussions followed by group reflection and evaluation.

This educational innovation aligns with ongoing efforts by institutions such as the Madhesh Institute of Health Sciences (MIHS), established to address regional disparities in healthcare education and services. MIHS and other provincial academies have begun academic programs but face challenges in modernizing curricula and pedagogical methods.

Integrating PBL into medical education represents a strategic investment in health system strengthening by producing a competent, locally responsive medical workforce. This approach fosters critical thinking, clinical reasoning, and community-oriented practice, essential for addressing Madhesh's unique health challenges. Funding support is critical to initiate, scale, and sustain this transformative educational model, contributing to improved healthcare outcomes and regional development.

Keywords: problem-based learning, student-centered education, medical education, Madhesh Province, health workforce development

Digital Transformation in Education

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Abstract

This abstract examines the current state and challenges of digital transformation in education, with a focus on Madhesh Province, Nepal. In today's information and technology-driven world, digital tools have become integral to teaching and learning. While some schools are equipped with computers, internet access, and digital labs, many either lack these resources or do not effectively utilize them. Traditional learning methods, reliant on teachers and textbooks, are rapidly evolving as students increasingly turn to digital sources such as Google, AI, virtual platforms (Zoom, AnyDesk), and learning management systems (Moodle) for knowledge acquisition. This shift enables continuous, flexible, and diverse learning opportunities beyond the classroom.

However, national data reveals significant gaps in digital integration: only 62% of schools use digital devices, 22% of students have sufficient access, and 58% use digital tools in class at least once a week. Internet connectivity is limited, with 12.7% of basic and 45% of secondary schools having internet access, while 70% have electricity (World Bank, 2023). Madhesh Province lags behind in all these indicators except electricity availability. A critical barrier is the lack of trained and skilled teachers proficient in digital pedagogy, many of whom prefer traditional manual teaching methods due to either reluctance or lack of training opportunities.

The solution lies not in the quantity of digital devices but in effective management and capacity building. Even a modest number of computers and peripherals, supported by dedicated teachers, can significantly enhance digital learning. Collaboration among local governments, provincial authorities, and schools is essential to provide training and resources. Given that most students own smartphones, leveraging these devices for virtual and self-directed learning can foster lifelong learning habits and make education more engaging and accessible.

Keywords: digital transformation, dedicated teacher, education, digital learning, Madhesh Province

Evidence Based practices in Talent Management

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Abstract

This paper explores the evolving landscape of Talent Management (TM) in the context of rapid technological disruption, globalization, and shifting workforce demographics, highlighting the transition from traditional intuition-based approaches to evidence-based, data-driven strategies. Drawing on multidisciplinary research from strategic human resource management, organizational behavior, and industrial practices, it examines how integrating scholarly research, organizational data, contextual understanding, and professional expertise enhances core TM functions such as talent identification, succession planning, leadership development, retention of high-potential employees, and workforce capability building.

The study emphasizes the growing importance of HR analytics, predictive modeling, and longitudinal talent tracking to provide real-time insights and enable proactive decision-making. Despite these advancements, barriers persist, including limited access to actionable research, low data literacy among HR professionals, and organizational resistance to change. The paper underscores the challenge of applying generalized research findings to specific organizational contexts, advocating for stronger collaboration between academics and practitioners to bridge this gap.

Furthermore, the research investigates how digital transformation and artificial intelligence are reshaping TM by enabling evidence-based talent forecasting, personalized development pathways, and reducing bias in talent decisions. Ethical considerations such as data privacy and equitable access to opportunities are also critically examined.

To institutionalize evidence-based TM, the paper calls for capacity building, leadership commitment, and the development of organizational learning systems that support sustainable performance in complex and competitive environments. By adopting these strategies, organizations can modernize talent management to better align with evolving workforce needs, enhance employee engagement, and maintain a competitive advantage.

Keywords: Talent Management, Evidence-Based HR Practices, HR Analytics, Strategic Human Resource Management, Digital Transformation

Exploring Gender Inequality in Madhesh Province: Challenges and Opportunities for Women's Empowerment

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Abstract

This research article critically examines gender inequality in Nepal's Madhesh Province, focusing on the structural, cultural, and socio-economic barriers impeding women's empowerment. Drawing on case studies and interviews with local women leaders, educators, and activists, the study reveals persistent discrimination rooted in patriarchal norms, limited access to education, healthcare, and political participation. The province exhibits some of the lowest gender development indicators nationally, with deep-rooted social practices such as son preference, child marriage, and restrictive citizenship laws further marginalizing women, especially in rural and marginalized communities.

The research highlights how gender-based violence, unequal educational opportunities, and economic exclusion continue to undermine women's agency and societal contributions. Women often face compounded disadvantages due to intersecting factors such as caste, poverty, and lack of legal recognition. Despite these challenges, the study identifies positive developments including awareness campaigns, education reforms, increased female leadership, and government initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality.

Policy recommendations emphasize the need for transformative actions to dismantle discriminatory norms, strengthen legal frameworks, and foster inclusive education and political participation. Empowering women through skills development, equitable access to resources, and community engagement is crucial to breaking cycles of inequality. The study also calls for enhanced collaboration among government bodies, civil society organizations, and international partners to address systemic barriers and promote sustainable progress.

In conclusion, achieving gender equality in Madhesh Province requires comprehensive, context-sensitive strategies that recognize and address the multifaceted nature of women's marginalization. By creating an enabling environment for women's empowerment, the province can unlock significant social and economic benefits, contributing to broader national development goals.

Keywords: gender inequality, women's empowerment, patriarchal norms, educational leadership, cultural practices, Madhesh Province

Towards Transformative Education in Madhesh Province: Reflections and Pathways

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Abstracts

This compilation, authored by an education expert and social philosopher deeply connected to the lived realities of Madhesh Province, presents a bold and visionary roadmap for educational transformation. It aims to confront entrenched disparities while inspiring provincial leaders, educators, and communities to collaboratively build an inclusive, equitable, and resilient education system. Each abstract within this collection is crafted to be both engaging and practical, grounded firmly in the local socio-cultural and economic context of Madhesh. The work offers innovative strategies and collaborative solutions that address key challenges such as access, quality, teacher capacity, and digital integration. By emphasizing community participation and context-sensitive reforms, the compilation advocates for a forward-thinking approach to education that not only responds to current needs but also anticipates future demands. This resource serves as a catalyst for meaningful dialogue and action among stakeholders committed to reshaping education in Madhesh Province, fostering sustainable development and social equity through transformative learning experiences.

Keywords: educational transformation, inclusive education, equitable learning, Madhesh Province, collaborative reform, digital education

Innovative Approaches to Teaching, Learning, and Assessment in Higher Education: A Qualitative Study of Blended Learning Integration

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Abstract

This study explores innovative teaching, learning, and assessment strategies through a blended learning model that integrates online and face-to-face instruction. Employing qualitative methods, it investigates teachers' and learners' experiences with blended modalities, focusing on instructional design, learner engagement, feedback mechanisms, and learning outcomes. The findings reveal that combining digital and in-person elements enhances flexibility, deepens engagement, and diversifies assessment practices.

A key component examined is the use of digital portfolios, which serve as dynamic, interactive platforms allowing students to document, reflect on, and showcase their learning progress over time. Digital portfolios support personalized learning by enabling students to select and present work that highlights their strengths and interests, fostering ownership and motivation. They also facilitate authentic and ongoing assessment, providing educators with comprehensive insights into student growth beyond traditional exams. Moreover, digital portfolios promote equity by accommodating diverse learning styles and enabling access from various locations, thus addressing barriers related to resources and opportunity.

The study highlights how digital portfolios, integrated within blended learning environments, contribute to more meaningful feedback and collaborative learning experiences. They prepare students for future academic and professional endeavors by developing critical self-reflection, digital literacy, and communication skills. The research underscores the importance of instructional design that leverages technology thoughtfully to enhance pedagogical effectiveness.

Implications for educational practice include the need for teacher training in digital tools, the incorporation of student-centered assessment strategies, and institutional support for blended learning infrastructures. By embracing these innovations, educational institutions can foster more engaging, flexible, and equitable learning environments that respond to diverse student needs.

Keywords: innovative teaching, learner engagement, blended learning, assessment strategy, digital portfolio

Nepal's Educational System and its Impact on Policy and Governance: A Review

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Abstract

To review Nepal Government policy and education governance.

Method: The researcher provides a thorough review of the research findings that have been published at the national and international levels. To analyse articles about policy and governance-related topics and combine the data, the researcher employed a scientific review technique called meta-analysis. Collecting research papers, reports, and data and conducting a comprehensive assessment in conjunction with thorough archival analysis would be the methods used for the scientific evaluation in a systematic way.

Finding: In Nepal, the constitution of 2015 provides for up to 12 years of free education in public schools. More than 11 universities have opened in Nepal, including Tribhuvan University (formerly the University of Nepal), Mahendra Sanskrit University, Purbanchal University, Lumbini Buddhist University (LBU), Agriculture and Forestry University (AFU), Mid-Western University (MWU), Far-Western University (FWU), Nepal Open University (NOU), and Rajarshi Janak University (RJU), Pradesh University, Birgunj, Pokhara University.

Recommendation: The Nepalese government offers three different kinds of education in Nepal, which prepares students for employment or entrepreneurship. First, secondary level education (up to the 12 pass). Give practical skills and training for market links. Secondly, mid-level (Bachelor and Master Level) human resource creation and provide opportunities for them to work in the private, public, and business sectors. Thirdly, high-level (MPhil, PhD, Post Doc, and DSc./D.Litt.) manpower production for planners, researchers, scientists, and monitoring and documentation preparation.

Free education up to the 12th grade was provided by the Nepalese government in schools at the government level. In Nepal, there are now over eleven open universities. These institutions are offering superior education. Students from technical institutes are unable to provide a quality education. Young people are better equipped to become entrepreneurs and work independently when they receive a good education and high standards. Always take into account production driven by the market and linkup production in the market since it fosters entrepreneurship and perfect education. Create workers at the basic, intermediate, and upper levels.

Keywords: review, status, policy, governance, action

Driving Educational Transformation: Informing Curriculum Modernization through Evidence-Based Research and Policy Synergy

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Abstract

This study examines the critical role of policymakers in embedding research and evidence-based practices within curriculum modernization efforts to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving global labor market. As education systems worldwide strive for equity, quality, and innovation, grounding policy decisions in robust educational research has become imperative. This research explores how policy frameworks can effectively translate educational research into practice, ensuring decisions at all levels are informed by reliable evidence. It analyzes successful international models where policies foster a culture of inquiry, data utilization, and accountability among educators.

Key discussions focus on designing evidence-informed policies, investing in research-practice partnerships—from initial needs assessments to curriculum revision and implementation monitoring—and leveraging empirical data on student learning outcomes and teacher readiness to guide curriculum updates aligned with 21st-century competencies. The study also addresses significant barriers to implementing evidence-based research, including limited access to research for educators and policymakers, resistance to curriculum change, and contextual constraints, offering actionable solutions to overcome these challenges.

Furthermore, the research highlights the importance of policy in building institutional capacity for continuous curriculum evaluation and fostering collaborative ecosystems among educators, researchers, and policymakers. Participants in the study gain a deeper understanding of critically evaluating and applying research findings across diverse educational settings, contributing to more responsive curricula and informed classroom practices.

By strengthening the link between research and curriculum policy, this approach empowers policymakers to lead meaningful educational transformation grounded in evidence and equity, ultimately preparing students to succeed in national and international markets.

Keywords: curriculum modernization, evidence-based policy, educational research, policymakers, educators, implementation strategies

Effectiveness of Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) Approach for Improving Foundational Literacy and Numeracy

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruption to education in Nepal, affecting over nine million children and resulting in severe learning loss equivalent to approximately three years of schooling, according to the World Bank. In response, the Government of Nepal introduced the Recovery and Accelerated Learning (ReAL) Plan to mitigate learning loss and institutionalize accelerated learning practices. Aligned with this plan, Street Child of Nepal (SCoN) implemented the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) approach targeting foundational literacy and numeracy skills among Grades 3–5 students.

TaRL employs tailored teaching and learning activities based on students' assessed learning levels, with progress measured periodically. Piloted in 64 schools during 2021–22 alongside partners such as Aasaman Nepal, Pratham Foundation, and the World Bank, the ten-week intervention demonstrated significant improvements. Subsequently, the program scaled to 600 community schools across Madhesh and Karnali provinces, reaching 36,000 children. A 2025 assessment of 12,782 students revealed literacy gains from 31.94% to 85.4% and numeracy improvements from 3.88% to 33.65%.

A comparative 2024 study involving 1,509 baseline and 1,489 endline students across 170 schools further confirmed that TaRL-intervened schools achieved substantially higher proficiency levels. At endline, 57.4% of students in TaRL schools attained the highest literacy proficiency (story level) compared to 31.6% in non-intervention schools; numeracy proficiency (division level) was 30.6% versus 8.8%, respectively.

These findings underscore the effectiveness of the TaRL approach and its potential for broader implementation as a research-backed strategy to accelerate learning recovery. Scaling TaRL can play a pivotal role in ensuring foundational competencies for children, contributing to Nepal's efforts to recover from pandemic-induced educational setbacks.

Keywords: learning loss, Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL), foundational literacy, numeracy, proficiency, accelerated learning

Failing of Medical Education System of Madhesh Pradesh: A Retrospective study

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Abstract

This study critically examines the persistent challenges facing the medical education system in Nepal's Madhesh Province despite the region's significant contribution to health personnel production. With eleven medical colleges operating in the province—out of seventy-four nationwide—Madhesh contributes approximately 14.86% of the country's health workforce. However, the system continues to face multifaceted problems that undermine the quality and effectiveness of medical education.

A retrospective narrative analysis was conducted using published data from the past decade, including academic articles, government surveys, news reports, and university records. The findings identify several key factors contributing to the system's underperformance: a dualistic educational structure, language barriers, outdated pedagogy, shortage of trained and qualified instructors, inadequate facilities, and insufficient budgeting. Political interference remains a dominant obstacle, impeding institutional development and governance reforms.

Notably, despite the early establishment of institutions like Janakpur and National Medical Colleges in 1999 and 2001, these colleges lag behind in quality and professional standards compared to counterparts elsewhere in Nepal. Accreditation processes are weak, and policy implementation often remains limited to documentation without effective enforcement or monitoring.

The study underscores the urgent need for strengthened governance, transparent budgeting, and capacity building to revitalize medical education in Madhesh. Without addressing political instability and systemic neglect, the province risks a deteriorating healthcare workforce and compromised future prospects for its youth.

In conclusion, the medical education system in Madhesh Province is hindered by structural, political, and resource-related challenges. Strategic reforms emphasizing quality assurance, faculty development, infrastructure improvement, and depoliticized governance are essential to ensure the production of competent healthcare professionals and to support the province's health sector development.

Keywords: medical education, health personnel, Madhesh Province, political interference, educational quality, governance

Action Planning for Future Curriculum Development

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of Action Research as a dynamic and cyclical methodology for future curriculum development, emphasizing teacher-led reflection and problem-solving to improve educational practices. Beginning with the identification of challenges faced by practitioners within their local contexts, the study involves planning interventions, implementing them in classrooms, observing outcomes, and collaboratively analyzing results with educators and colleagues. This iterative process fosters continuous improvement and bridges the gap between theory and practice.

The research highlights the interconnectedness of eco-socio-economic planning and educational administration, advocating for curriculum development that aligns legal policies, strategic planning, and effective administration. It underscores the importance of collaboration between resource managers and the scientific community to adapt curricula to evolving environmental and societal needs. Recognizing that no single approach fits all contexts, the paper stresses tailoring curriculum development to stakeholder objectives and decision-making environments.

Drawing on established models of action research, the paper proposes a six-stage cyclical framework: (a) identifying focus areas, (b) conducting needs analysis, (c) developing action plans, (d) implementing interventions, (e) evaluating outcomes, and (f) reflecting on the process. This model views curriculum development as a practice-based, problem-solving, continuous, and context-dependent endeavor.

By empowering teachers as both producers and users of educational knowledge, action research promotes ownership, relevance, and sustainability in curriculum reform. The approach encourages inclusive practices and integration of ICT to address local realities, particularly in regions like Madhesh Province. Ultimately, this methodology supports the co-creation of curricula that are responsive, equitable, and resilient, fostering meaningful educational transformation.

Keywords: curriculum, development, action research, inclusive education, ICT, Madhesh Province

AI Architecture: In Educational Transformation

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Abstract

This paper explores AI Architecture as a foundational framework for advancing artificial intelligence systems in educational transformation. AI Architecture integrates critical components such as student motivation, faculty and student adoption of technology, data sources, processing units, algorithms, models, and user interfaces into a cohesive system. The study identifies three core aspects: structural design that connects students and institutions through data pipelines, learning models, and computational resources; transformation processes involving hardware and software that convert raw inputs into intelligent outputs; and data infrastructure rooted in classroom activities and syllabi, emphasizing multimodal data as essential for AI operations.

Focusing on education, the paper proposes an AI-integrated classroom model that aligns digital education objectives with technology-driven teaching philosophies and data-informed instructional behaviors. This model highlights transformational opportunities for learners, facilitators, and institutional stakeholders. The research demonstrates that well-designed AI systems can bridge traditional education with smart learning environments, fostering enhanced engagement and personalized learning.

Findings underscore the importance of balancing technical architecture with human factors to realize meaningful educational transformation. Implementing AI Architecture requires thoughtful integration of machine learning frameworks, educational technology, and robust data infrastructure to support digital transformation goals.

Keywords: AI Architecture, machine learning framework, educational technology, data infrastructure, digital transformation

Problem Based Learning (PBL); a New Teaching-learning Method in Medical Education of Madhesh

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Abstract

A facilitator helps students work in small groups to solve realworld problems as part of the teaching technique known as problem-based learning (PBL).The goal of a facilitator is to help the students learn new things and develop their problem-solving abilities.Problem Based Learning can help students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, creative and analytical skills—all of which are vital in the twenty-first century because they can improve people's lives.Research indicates that PBL improves knowledge comprehension and retention when compared to regular lectures. The purpose of study is to implement Problem Based Learning as a core teaching strategy in medical colleges of Madhesh Province,toimprove teamwork and communication skills among students and align medical education with international best practices.

PBL has been successfully applied in Nepal by establishments such as Patan Academy of Health Sciences and Kathmandu University School of Medical Sciences, proving its value in improving medical education. By implementing PBL, Madhesh Province may update its medical curriculum and generate graduates who are more qualified to handle the area's healthcare demands.

Methodology: PBL can be implemented by: a) Curriculum Design, b) Faculty Training, c) Student Orientation, d) Resource Allocation and e) Assessment.

Expected Outcomes of Study: Enhanced Learning Outcomes, Increased Student Engagement, Improved Teamwork Skills and Alignment with Global Standards.

The adoption of problem-based learning in Madhesh Province's medical schools is a big step in the direction of modernizing medical education and creating qualified medical practitioners. PBL may change the educational landscape of the area with proper planning, sufficient funding, and dedication from all parties involved.

Keywords: curriculum, facilitators, problem-based learning

Impact of Conflict Management on Employees' Performance in a Private Sector Organization in Nepal

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of dispute resolution techniques on employee performance within private sector organizations. It specifically examines five conflict management strategies: Competing, Avoiding, Accommodating, Compromising, and Collaborating. Utilizing a descriptive survey design, data were collected through a self-developed questionnaire incorporating the Employee Performance Questionnaire alongside a Conflict Management Strategies inventory. The research aimed to determine how these dispute resolution approaches influence workers' productivity and overall performance.

Findings reveal that effective conflict management strategies significantly affect employee performance, highlighting the importance of addressing workplace disagreements proactively rather than ignoring them. The study emphasizes that unresolved conflicts can undermine productivity, morale, and organizational cohesion, whereas skillful resolution fosters a positive work environment conducive to enhanced performance.

Based on these results, the study recommends comprehensive behavioral training for employees at all organizational levels to equip them with the necessary skills to manage conflicts constructively. Such training should focus on recognizing conflict sources, selecting appropriate resolution techniques, and fostering collaborative communication. Additionally, supervisors and managers should receive continuous professional development to strengthen their capacity to mediate disputes effectively and support team dynamics.

The research underscores that conflict is an inevitable aspect of organizational life; thus, cultivating a culture that values open dialogue and constructive conflict resolution is essential for sustaining high employee productivity. By integrating targeted conflict management training into organizational development programs, private sector organizations can improve workforce performance, reduce turnover, and enhance overall operational effectiveness.

In conclusion, this study affirms that dispute resolution techniques are critical determinants of employee performance. Organizations that invest in developing conflict management competencies among their workforce are better positioned to achieve sustainable productivity gains and foster a harmonious workplace.

Keywords: dispute resolution, conflict management strategies, employee performance, workplace productivity, private sector.

Challenges and Opportunities in Madhesh Province

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Educational Improvement Committee

Committee is a registered organization by Dhanusha District Administrative office, Janakpurdham.

Abstract

This analysis by the Educational Improvement Committee examines the multifaceted challenges and opportunities facing the education sector in Nepal's Madhesh Province. The province grapples with a rapidly growing population that strains existing educational infrastructure and resources, resulting in insufficient institutional capacity to accommodate all students. Many learners cross national borders seeking better-skilled education due to limited local opportunities and economic constraints. Schools and colleges, categorized as constituent, public, and private, suffer from unequal teacher distribution, with shortages particularly acute from lower to higher education levels.

Key challenges include inadequate infrastructure, resource deficits, teacher shortages and quality concerns, digital literacy gaps, and marginalization of disadvantaged communities. The province also faces difficulties in higher education and skill development, low literacy rates, weak coordination and accountability mechanisms, and population pressures exacerbated by in-migration from mountainous and hill regions. These factors collectively hinder educational progress and quality outcomes.

Despite these obstacles, the province holds significant opportunities. Community engagement initiatives, increased investment, targeted interventions, and digital literacy programs offer pathways to improvement. Efforts to enhance higher education and skill development, ensure quality assurance, and create safe, inclusive learning environments are underway. Addressing population growth and controlling in-migration can also help balance demand and resources.

Madhesh Province's high population density contrasts with underutilized natural resources and comparatively low government funding for education. Literacy rates remain below national averages, posing substantial barriers to secondary and higher education advancement. Recent data reveal declining educational standards, with low pass rates in key examinations attributed to teacher shortages, poor infrastructure, political interference, and governance challenges. Coordinated efforts among students, educators, local governments, and provincial authorities are essential to reverse this trend and improve educational quality.

In conclusion, Madhesh Province's education system faces critical challenges that require comprehensive, collaborative strategies emphasizing resource allocation, teacher capacity building, infrastructure development, and inclusive policies to unlock its educational potential.

Keywords: digital literacy, infrastructure, marginalized communities, quality assurance, skilled education, Madhesh Province

Book Review: Artificial and Emotional Intelligence for Employee Engagement with E-Human Resource Management

Publisher: Mission Printing and Publication Pvt. Ltd. (Nepal)

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Abstract

"Artificial and Emotional Intelligence for Employee Engagement with E-Human Resource Management" is a timely and insightful exploration of the intersection between emerging technologies and the human dimensions of organizational life. Divided into four comprehensive sections—Artificial Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Employee Engagement, and E-HRM—the book offers a balanced, practical, and critical perspective on how these domains converge to shape the future of work.

The author's candid reflection on the rapidly evolving landscape of AI is both refreshing and necessary. Unlike many works that either sensationalize or overcomplicate the subject, this book maintains a grounded, practitioner-oriented approach. The author's independence as a researcher shines through, providing readers with an honest appraisal of both the promises and pitfalls of AI in HR. The narrative acknowledges the "moving target" nature of AI development and the challenges this presents for both research and implementation.

A standout feature of the book is its emphasis on actionable intelligence. Rather than dwelling on abstract theory, the author consistently translates complex concepts into practical guidance for HR professionals, managers, and organizational leaders. The discussion of emotional intelligence is particularly noteworthy, highlighting the irreplaceable value of human skills—compassion, creativity, and empathy—even as automation and algorithms become more prevalent in the workplace.

The book does not shy away from the ethical dilemmas posed by AI, such as bias, dehumanization, and exclusion in hiring and management processes. The author calls for the establishment of ethical standards and responsible leadership to ensure that technology enhances, rather than undermines, the human experience at work. This ethical lens is a crucial contribution, urging readers to remember that technology is only as humane as the people who design and deploy it.

Employee engagement and E-HRM are treated with equal depth, with the author arguing convincingly that investing in engagement is a strategic imperative, not just an HR initiative. The integration of AI and emotional intelligence into digital HR platforms is presented as a means to scale personalized, meaningful experiences for employees, ultimately driving organizational performance and satisfaction.

In conclusion, this book is an essential read for HR professionals, business leaders, and anyone interested in the future of work. It offers a rare combination of technical insight, ethical reflection, and practical advice, all delivered in an accessible and engaging style. The central message is clear: technology will continue to transform the workplace, but it is our human values and skills that will determine whether this transformation leads to progress or peril.

Highly recommended for those seeking to navigate the evolving world of HR with both intelligence and humanity.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, emotional intelligence, employee, Engagement, E-HRM, HR Technology, Ethics, Organizational Change

Chapter Review: Human Development - Vision of Yoga

A Reference Book on Comparative Assessment from the Eastern Approach
Published: March 2022

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Publisher: Intellectual's Book Palace

ISBN: 978-9937-9523-9-2

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Abstract

Overview

This chapter presents a rich exploration of human development through the Eastern philosophical lens, especially Hindu cosmology and yogic thought.

Key Themes

1. **Contrasting Views on Human Evolution** Western science views human progress as biological and intellectual evolution from animalistic origins to modern civilization. In contrast, the Eastern perspective sees the universe and humans evolving cyclically—from spiritual to material and back—guided by universal intelligence (vijñāna-vijrīmbhitani). This cyclical process is reflected in the Hindu concept of yugas (ages), where spiritual evolution persists even during times of apparent decline, such as the Kali Yuga.
2. **The Cyclical Nature of Existence** The chapter explains creation and dissolution as a continuous cycle—from subtle causes (karana) to gross manifestation (sthūla) and back—mirroring cosmic rhythms. Human development is thus an eternal process of expansion and contraction, not mere linear progress.
3. **Mind, Body, and Self-Mastery** Humans differ from animals by their ability to transcend bodily impulses (prana) through intellectual and moral development. While intellect helps move beyond body-centered awareness (dehatmaka-buddhi), it must be balanced with purified emotions for true self-mastery.
4. **Yoga and Self-Realization** Yoga is presented as the path to freedom from dualities of virtue and vice, leading to equanimity and spiritual awakening (citing Bhagavad Gita 2:50). Human development culminates in union with the divine (Narayan), symbolized by the ever-turning wheel of Brahma.

Understanding Human Behavior: The Gunas and Motivation

The chapter delves into the three gunas—Sattva (purity), Rajas (activity), and Tamas (inertia)—which shape human nature and behavior. Tamas, associated with ignorance and inertia, is exemplified by Prince Duryodhana’s envy and destructive impulses in the Mahabharata. Envy, as discussed by Gurucharan Das and Freud, can fuel both destructive tendencies and the quest for justice.

The gunas also influence daily rhythms:

- Morning (Sattva): Ideal for planning and intellectual work
- Daytime (Rajas): Suited for energetic, action-oriented tasks
- Night (Tamas): Time for rest and socializing
- Through intuitive perception, these qualities manifest as subtle energies with distinct colors and waveforms, forming the basis of cosmic elements (Panchamahabhoota).

Practical Management Insights

- Drawing from Kautilya’s Arthashastra, the chapter maps motivational strategies to the gunas:
- Sattva: Persuasion (Sama), ethical conduct (Niti)
- Rajas: Rewards (Dama), internal competition (Bheda)
- Tamas: Discipline and punishment (Danda)

Effective leadership requires discerning individuals’ dominant guna and applying a mix of these methods accordingly. For example, Sattvik individuals respond best to ethical appeals, Rajasic to incentives and competition, and Tamasic to firm discipline.

Conclusion

This chapter offers a profound comparative assessment of human development, integrating Eastern spiritual insights with practical motivational frameworks. It underscores that true progress transcends physical and intellectual growth, culminating in spiritual evolution and self-realization. By understanding the dynamic interplay of the gunas, leaders can foster harmony, motivation, and growth within organizations, aligning human nature with higher consciousness.

Section Review: Vision for a Prosperous Madhesh with Thriving Madhesi Communities

Knowing Madhesh Province of Nepal. In Revitalizing Tourism: Strategies for Sustainable Growth and Development (pp. 1–14). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14252283>

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Abstract

This section outlines a compelling vision for Madhesh Province as a prosperous, vibrant region characterized by happy and economically empowered Madhesi communities. Recognized as Nepal's agricultural heartland, Madhesh benefits from fertile plains and flat terrain, offering immense potential for both agricultural advancement and industrial growth. The province has already demonstrated strong revenue-generating capacity, surpassing other regions, yet faces critical challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and insufficient access to quality education and healthcare. These deficits have contributed to rising illiteracy, poor health outcomes, and persistent poverty among many residents.

To transform this potential into reality, the section emphasizes the urgent need to cultivate an entrepreneurial ecosystem that nurtures local talent and innovation. Developing the right skills and attitudes among the population is seen as key to overcoming unemployment. Strategic investment in small-scale, agro-based industries—such as food processing, ornamental crafts, and IT enterprises—can generate substantial employment opportunities while stimulating local economies.

Agriculture remains the backbone of Madhesh's economy. The section advocates for sustainable farming practices, adoption of modern technologies, and farmer empowerment through training programs, cooperative models, and improved access to credit. These measures aim to boost productivity and enhance farmers' livelihoods, thereby raising the overall quality of life in the province. Many provisions found in Policy of Madhesh e.g Custom Hiring, Lotus Farming illustrate research based policy formulation in Madhesh.

Additionally, Madhesh's favorable climate and supportive government policies position it as an attractive destination for renewable energy investment, particularly solar power. Harnessing solar energy offers dual benefits: fostering sustainable development and creating new jobs. The vision encourages investors to capitalize on this opportunity, positioning Madhesh as a leader in Nepal's green energy sector.

In summary, the section presents a holistic strategy for Madhesh's development—leveraging natural resources, enhancing human capital through targeted training, promoting cooperative frameworks, and implementing supportive policies. It calls for collective commitment from all stakeholders to realize a future where meaningful employment and improved living standards are accessible to all residents. The path to a prosperous Madhesh is clear and achievable through shared vision and concerted action.

Keywords: agro-based industries, Custom Hiring, Lotus Farming, revenue-generating capacity

Stakeholder Satisfaction and Its Impact on Institutional Quality Support Systems: A Study of Community Colleges in Bagmati Province, Nepal

Tara Prasad Gautam

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between stakeholder satisfaction and the effectiveness of Institutional Quality Support Systems (IQSS) perform in community colleges in Bagmati Province, Nepal, and how happy the people who use them are with them. It looks at how the perspectives of diverse groups, like students, professors and staff, the college administration, parents and guardians, people who live in the area, and business partners, affect the quality of the school. The design comprises both qualitative and quantitative parts. We used structured surveys to get information from 645 stakeholders at 10 community institutions that were picked for a specific reason.. The study examine at satisfaction levels, IQSS indicators, and how the kind, location, and size of the institution affected them using chi-square tests, regression, ANOVA, and descriptive statistics. This is one of the first studies in Nepal to study at how satisfied different groups of people are with community colleges and how that affects their internal quality systems. It gives institutions a mechanism to collect feedback from stakeholders on their quality assurance efforts that is both theoretical and practical. The results show that institutions need to adapt to focus on participatory governance, services that listen to stakeholders, stronger infrastructure, and more organized career services. Policy reforms are needed to make IQSS better with the support of stakeholders. For instance, rural schools should get more money from the provinces, and the UGC should have training that is up to date.

Keywords: stakeholder satisfaction, institutional quality support system, community colleges, higher education, nepal, iqms, governance, feedback mechanism

Strengthening Children's Reading Habits through Home-Based Learning Corners: A Scalable Model by Aasaman Nepal

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Abstract

A recent observation revealed that a majority of school-aged children are not engaging in reading or academic activities at home, often spending time playing before and after school and showing limited respect for parental guidance. This lack of structured study time has contributed to declining learning outcomes. In response, Aasaman Nepal initiated a home-based Learning Corner intervention to promote regular reading habits and improve academic discipline among Children.

The Home based Learning Corner provides a dedicated and safe space for children to study within their own homes, encouraging consistent engagement with education beyond school hours. This initiative supports families in creating the corner using locally available resources, while also providing essential learning and reading materials. Parental engagement has been crucial. It makes parents more responsible toward child right protection and positive caring of the child as well. The teachers and School Management Committee (SMC) members mobilized for door-to-door visits to monitor progress and provide support and an encouragement as well. Additionally, orientations on positive parenting are conducted with mothers' groups to reinforce the importance of parental support and conversation with their children in the Learning process.

Feedback from children and parents has been collected through interviews and community meetings, revealing strong appreciation for the Learning Corner approach. Children have shown increased focus, improved study routines, and a growing interest in reading. Parents have become more engaged in their children's education, creating a more friendly and respectful home learning culture.

Expected outcomes include a sustained and enriching learning environment at home, stronger reading habits contributing to lifelong skills, improved academic performance, enhanced parent-child relationships, and a heightened sense of responsibility among students. This community-supported and resource-efficient model shows strong potential for scaling up across similar contexts to address foundational learning gaps in Madhesh.

Keywords: Home-based Learning, Learning Corner, Reading Habit, Parental Engagement, Community- Based Education

Inclusive and Equitable Education

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Abstract

Madhesh province is encouraging and supporting the entire community to get education through learning environment. Province not restricting only to children with disabilities but also takes in gender, caste, children with different learning needs, marginalized and economically deprived communities. However, literacy rate of Madhesh province stands 63.5%, whereas the national's literacy rate 76.2% by the census report of Nepal 2021. In the comparison of the national literacy rate of Nepal 77.4%, the men literacy rate is 77.9%, while the women literacy rate is 59.9%, which highlighting a significant gender gap in the Inclusive and Equitable Education (IEE). Also 41.25% (10-17 years) girls are out of school in Madhesh Province. This is exceptionally high compared to the national average of the total children never going to formal educational school.

The Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) has put in place a series of policy frameworks like Provincial education policy, ongoing progression of the Local Education Plan into responsive actions and resources to promote the IEE. In addition, Federal Government of Nepal (GoN) has rolled out their new School Education Sector Plan (SESP), which specifically outlines their approaches to ensuring the IEE within the education system and is working to implement a comprehensive National Equity Strategy.

To ensure greater the IEE, province should strongly apply the regular screening in the classroom, need-based accessible materials and learning corners, tailoring the appropriate pedagogy for the IEE. Also requires the solid instruction to produce the School Improvement Plan (SIP) to develop innovative approaches like Universal Design for Learning and Assessment (UDLA). Province should continue the unique campaign like Mukhyamantri Beti Padhau Beti Bachaun to address the problems in the protection, education and empowerment of girls enrollment in the IEE as well as Beti Jindabad campaign initiated by the Ministry of Sports and Social Welfare.

Keywords: equity, inclusive education, learning for all, marginalization

Sustainability of Public Colleges Retaining Lecturers through Innovative and Proactive Leadership

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Abstract

Lecturers' retention is a challenging issue in public colleges since their turnover rate is sensitive, therefore, innovative and proactive leadership is key element to address the very trend by the means of different kinds of attractive provisions to empower lecturers' to check turnover rate.

This study aims at exploring the fundamental reasons behind lecturers' turnover from public colleges and analyzes the existing human resource provision of public colleges to motivate their professional development associating the commitment of existing college regulation, practices, complimentarily with university as well.

Empirical research was applied. Public colleges of Nepal were population and public colleges of Madhesh were sample. Strata were made to select sample colleges and lecturers. Data was collected through in depth interview to collect lecturers' perception and existing human resource (HR) policy provisions were studied using historical study through library study. Abraham Maslow's 'Need Hierarchy Theory' was linked with lecturers' perception for analysis of the issue of the study.

The findings reveal that prevailing provisions are inadequate to motivate lecturers' in terms of their financial security, career path, professional development and individual growth in changing scenario. Similarly the policy level management practices lack farsighted perspectives in globally dynamic HR dimensions and lacks the authentic analysis of external HR environment. Similarly grievance handling practices is weak that is leading venerable institutional relation provoking internal conflicts [Industrial Relation].

Top level management of the public colleges need to restructure the management practices substituting the traditional one with contingent approach that can yield fruitful results being adjusted with particular situation. HR policies must be proactive to address the lecturers' need and aspirations for sustainability of public colleges though innovative leadership instead of traditional and reactive.

Keywords: Public colleges, lecturers' retention, prospective and innovative leadership, sustainability, institutional relation.

The Confluence of Language and Life: Whole-Person Learning in ESL Education

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Abstract

In this study, the use of whole-person learning in English as a Second Language (ESL) is perceived at different prospects of students-thinking, feelings, social interactions, and physical activities. It is tried to explore how whole-person learning is practiced, the problems faced, and what results come from using these methods in ESL settings are the prime concern of this study. The study collects data from interviews with ESL teachers, observations of classrooms, and stories collected from students to show how this different approach can help build language skills and support personal growth.

This research focuses on how whole-person learning is used in ESL programs and what effects it has on students' language skills, motivation, and personal growth. It considers how emotional understanding and cultural context can enhance ESL learning. By using whole-person methods, the article examines how such practices encourage learners to connect more with the language, improving skills and critical thinking.

With this, the research study states the application of the teaching methods for bringing students' sensory wellbeing, knowledge to respect culture, values and assumption and communal relation. It is to implement by integrating whole person learning with the theories underlying like Vygotsky's concept on social learning and Maslow theory of need hierarchy.

The research connects motivation, social learning, and school performance and gives practical ideas for ESL teachers to create friendly and adaptable classrooms.

Keywords: Whole-person, ESL classrooms, Multiple Intelligence, Holistic, Humanistic education, Interpersonal

Implementation of Science and ICT Education and Access for Marginalized Communities in Government Schools of Sarlahi, Nepal

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Abstract

This study assessed the implementation status of science and ICT education in government secondary schools of Sarlahi District in Madhesh Pradesh, alongside the accessibility of these schools for marginalized groups, particularly OBC and Muslim children. Utilizing a descriptive-cum-exploratory research design, quantitative data were gathered via simple random sampling of secondary students using structured interviews, complemented by purposive sampling for qualitative in-depth interviews with school administrators. Results indicated that although 92.4 percent of students reported science teacher availability, staffing shortages persist in some schools. Only 29.7 percent rated science laboratories as good, with 30.3 percent rating those poor, highlighting infrastructural deficiencies. Laboratory use was limited revealing a gap between theory and practice. ICT integration remained minimal, with 20 percent reporting regular use in teaching. The school environment was largely inclusive, with 70.8 percent reporting no discrimination, yet 28.4 percent felt excluded from decision-making. Positive perceptions were noted in safety, teacher-student rapport, peer respect, and cultural sensitivity, though improvements are needed. The findings underscore the necessity of enhancing resource provision, promoting inclusivity, and fostering collaborative governance to advance educational quality and equity in these schools.

Keywords: Science Education, ICT Integration, Marginalized Communities, School Inclusivity, Educational Infrastructure

उच्च शिक्षा सुधारका सवालमा सामुदायिक क्याम्पसका बाध्यताहरू

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Abstract

उच्च शिक्षालाई अनुसन्धानमुखी र व्यावहारिक गुणस्तर सुधारको आधार बनाइनु आवश्यक छ । नेपालको संविधान २०७२ को भाग ४ धारा ५१ (ज), दफा (३) मा 'उच्च शिक्षालाई सहज, गुणस्तरीय र पहुँचयोग्य बनाई क्रमशः निःशुल्क बनाउँदै लैजाने' सन्दर्भ छ । त्यस्तै राष्ट्रिय शिक्षा नीति २०७६ दफा ९.१२ मा पनि 'गुणस्तरीय मान्यता तथा अन्तर्राष्ट्रिय स्तरको सान्दर्भिक उच्च शिक्षा' को प्रसङ्ग छ । दिगो विकासको लक्ष्य, सोह्रौँ पञ्चवर्षीय योजना, विद्यालय क्षेत्र विकास योजना आदिले उच्च शिक्षाको गुणस्तर सुधारमा व्यावहारिक कार्यान्वयनको अपेक्षा गरेको पाइन्छ । यद्यपि नेपालमा निजी, सामुदायिक र सरकारी क्याम्पसको फरक वर्गीकरण र व्यवहारका कारण प्रभुत्व वर्ग र सीमान्त वर्गले पढ्ने शैक्षिक निकाय तथा विषय क्षेत्र नै फरक रहेको देखिन्छ । स्थानीय सरकारले स्थानीय सरकार सञ्चालन ऐन, २०७४ अनुसार विद्यालयीय शिक्षामै ध्यान दिनु पनि सान्दर्भिक नै देखिन्छ । अर्कोतिर प्रदेश सरकारले विधानतः आफ्नो प्रदेशभित्रका सम्बन्धन प्राप्त क्याम्पसप्रति कम चासो दिने र माउ क्याम्पसले सबैभन्दा बढी जनशक्ति उत्पादन गरिरहेका सामुदायिक क्याम्पसलाई मूलतः आफ्नो आम्दानी स्रोतका रूपमा लिने अघोषित यथार्थका कारण यस्ता क्याम्पसहरू सबैभन्दा बढी मारमा परेको देखिन्छ । विश्वविद्यालय अनुदान आयोगबाट प्राप्त अनुदानको सीमित रकमका भरमा विद्यार्थी सङ्ख्या कम भएका सामुदायिक क्याम्पसहरूले उच्च शिक्षाको गुणस्तरका मापदण्ड अनुरूप आपूर्तिलाई रुपान्तरित

गर्न नसक्नु प्रमुख बाध्यता हो । यसर्थ उच्च शिक्षा सुधारका सवालमा सामुदायिक क्याम्पसका बाध्यतालाई निःक्रयोल गर्नु नै यस अध्ययनको मुख्य उद्देश्य रहेको छ । यस अध्ययनबाट मधेश प्रदेशका धेरैजसो छिमेकी सामुदायिक क्याम्पसहरुबिचमा विद्यार्थी तानातान हुने, एकै खालका कार्यक्रम सञ्चालन गरिने, विद्यार्थीको आम्दानीबाट क्याम्पसको खर्च धान्न नसक्ने, स्थानीय सरकार र दाताहरूसँग हारगुहार गरिरहनुपर्नेलगायतका समस्याका कारण गुणस्तर सुधारमा समस्या रहेको पाइयो । यसर्थ यस अध्ययनबाट आवश्यकता अध्ययन गरी क्याम्पसलाई प्रभावकारी रूपले व्यवस्थापन गर्नुपर्ने, मुलुकलाई आवश्यक पर्ने जनशक्तिको सर्वेक्षण गरी कार्यक्रमहरुलाई समायोजन गर्नुपर्ने तथा गुणस्तर मापदण्डका आधारमा स्तरीकरण गरी प्रदेश सरकारले अपनत्व ग्रहण गर्नुपर्ने निष्कर्ष प्राप्त भएको छ ।

मुख्य शब्दावली : गुणस्तर, जनशक्ति, निरपेक्ष गरिबी, प्रभुत्व वर्ग, सीमान्त वर्ग ।

मधेशमा मातृभाषामा शिक्षा: भोजपुरी भाषाको विश्लेषणात्मक अध्ययन

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लेखसार

बहुभाषी शिक्षणबाट विद्यार्थीको विद्यालयप्रति आकर्षण बढ्ने, बिचैमा विद्यालय छाड्ने विद्यार्थी सङ्ख्या नियन्त्रणमा सहयोग पुग्ने, विद्यालयप्रति जनअपनत्व बढ्दा जनसहभागिता अभिवृद्धि हुने, शैक्षिक उपलब्धि बढ्नेलगायत फाइदा प्राप्त गर्न सकिन्छ । शिक्षामा मातृभाषाको प्रयोगले सिकाइको व्यवधानलाई निस्तेज पार्दै विद्यार्थीमा सामाजिकीकरण विकास गर्न, विद्यार्थीको संज्ञानात्मक विकासमा मद्दत गर्न, भाषा तथा संस्कृतिको पहिचान र संरक्षण गर्न र अन्ततोगत्वा भाषिक विविधतालाई सम्बोधन गर्दै राष्ट्रिय एकतालाई समेत सुदृढ पार्न मद्दत पुग्ने मत सर्वमान्य छ । यसै परिवेशमा नेपालको संविधानद्वारा धारा ५१ (ग)(७) माराष्ट्रमा बहुभाषिक नीति अपनाउनुपर्ने भने लक्ष्यतय गरिएको छ । उपरोक्त उद्देश प्राप्त गर्न हेतु मातृभाषामा शिक्षा प्राप्त गर्ने अधिकारलाई शिक्षासम्बन्धी अधिकारअन्तर्गत धारा ३१(५) अन्तर्गत मौलिक अधिकारको रूपमा समेत उल्लेख गरिएको छ । त्यस्तै, अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क शिक्षासम्बन्धी ऐन, २०७५ मा प्रत्येक नेपाली समुदायलाई आफ्नो मातृभाषामा अध्ययन गर्ने प्रबन्ध सुनिश्चित गरिएको छ । यस सम्बन्धमा आवश्यक नीतिगत सवालहरूका सम्बन्धमा सरकारलाई सिफारिस गर्न भाषा आयोगको गठन पनि भएको छ । यद्यपि, केही सीमित स्थानिय तहहरूमा बाहेक मातृभाषामा शिक्षणको पूर्वाधार तयार गरी त्यसलाई लागु गर्न मधेश प्रदेशका अधिकांश स्थानिय सरकारहरू असमर्थ व अनिच्छुक देखिएका दुखद यथार्थ हामीसँग छ । यसले संवैधानिक तथा कानुनी उद्देश्यलाई दुरूह मात्र बनाएको छैन, संघीयताको सबलिकरणलाई पनि निस्तेज बनाएको छ । तसर्थ, मधेश

प्रदेशमा बोलिने विभिन्न भाषाहरूमध्ये यस लेखको प्रयोजनार्थ प्राज्ञिक सहजताका लागि दोश्रो ठूलो संख्यामा मातृभाषि रहेको भोजपुरी भाषामा शिक्षणका सन्दर्भमा भएका असल प्रयासहरू, त्यहाँ देखिएका उपलब्धिका साथै व्यावहारिक तहमा देखिएका चुनौतीहरूबारे चिन्तन-मन्थन गर्ने अभिप्रायले यस कार्यपत्रमा आवश्यक बौद्धिक-विमर्शको प्रयत्न गरिने छ । यसका साथै, प्रस्तुत लेखमा भोजपुरी भाषामा शिक्षा प्रदान गर्ने सम्बन्धमा मधेश प्रदेशका विभिन्न शिक्षासम्बद्ध निकायहरू जस्तै शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालय, शिक्षा विकास निर्देशनालय, विद्यालय, भाषिक समुदाय, नागरिक समाजलगायतको भुमिका केकस्तो हुनुपर्छ तथा भाषा आयोगले तत्काल यस मामिलामा केकस्तो पहलकदमी लिनुपर्छ भन्ने सवालहरूको अन्वेषणतर्फ समेत परिणाममुखी भई केही आधारभुत निष्कर्ष पहिल्याउन कोशिस गर्नेछ ।

मुख्य शब्दावली : मातृभाषा , शिक्षा , भोजपुरी , विद्यालय , मधेश , विद्यार्थी

समावेशी तथा समतामूलक शिक्षा

Inclusive and Equitable Education

डा. ज्ञानी यादव

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लेखसार

समाजिक न्याय र समानता प्राप्त गर्न शिक्षा सबैभन्दा ठूलो उपकरण हो, जसले समावेशी समुदाय र समाजको विकासमा प्रभाव पार्छ । समावेशी शिक्षा नेपालको सन्दर्भमा एउटा नौलो अवधारणा हो । यो नयाँ अवधारणा स्पेनको सालामाङ्कामा सन् १९९४ मा शुरुवात भै हाम्रो देशमा आ.ब. २०५३।०५४ देखि समावेशी शिक्षा कार्यक्रम कार्यान्वयनमा आएको हो । समावेशी शिक्षाले उत्तरदायी, सम्मानजनक र सहयोगी सिकाइ वातावरण मार्फत समाजका सबै बालबालिकाहरूको विविध आवश्यकता र रुचीहरूलाई सम्बोधन गरी शिक्षाको मूलप्रवाहमा ल्याई शिक्षा दिने दृष्टिकोण र प्रकृया विश्वव्यापी सिद्धान्त हो । शिक्षाको अवसरबाट वञ्चित भएका गरिब, दलित, अपाङ्ग, द्वन्द्वपीडित, असहाय अनाथ, सुकुमवासी, बालश्रमिक, सडक बालबालिका, भाषिक कठिनाई भएका, भौगोलिक, समाजिक र साँस्कृतिक कारणले पिछडिएका विविध खालका बालबालिकाहरूलाई उनीहरूकै आवश्यकता, क्षमता, चाहना, रुची र उमेर अनुसारको शैक्षिक वातावरण उपलब्ध गराएर शिक्षा दिनु पर्छ भन्ने कुरामा समावेशी शिक्षाले जोड दिन्छ ।

बालकेन्द्रीत शिक्षण सिकाइ, विविधताको सम्बोधन, मानव अधिकारको पूर्ण प्रयोजन, शिक्षा प्रणालीको कार्यकुशलता, लागत प्रभावकारितामा सुधार, र न्यायसंगत अंशियारी आदि समावेशी शिक्षाको सिद्धान्तहरू हुन् ।

समावेशी शिक्षा कार्यक्रमलाई प्रभावकारी रूपमा कार्यान्वयन गर्ने क्रममा आधारभूत तथा प्राथमिक शिक्षा परियोजना, प्रथम र दोश्रो, सबैका लागि शिक्षा कार्यक्रम, विद्यालय क्षेत्र सुधार

कार्यक्रम आदि कार्यान्वयन भएका छन् । यसरी समावेशी शिक्षा एक बहुयामिक र बहुपक्षीय प्रकृया हो, जसको मुख्य उद्देश्य सबै प्रकारका बालबालिकाहरूलाई शिक्षण प्रकृत्यामा सत्रिमय रूपले संलग्न गराउनु हो ।

समतामूलक शिक्षा (Equitable Education) को अर्थ सबै विद्यार्थीहरूलाई सफल हुनको लागि उनीहरूको व्यक्तिगत आवश्यकता वा भिन्नता अनुसार श्रोतसाधनमा समान पहुँच प्रदान गर्दछ । शिक्षामा समान अवसरको नीतिले सबैलाई भेदभावविहिन तवरमा शिक्षा प्रदान गर्ने नीति त ल्यायो, तर यस नीतिका वावजुद्ध विद्यालय जाने उमेरका बालबालिकामध्ये एउटा ठूलो हिस्सा गरिबी, अन्धविश्वास, भाषा, भूगोल आदि विविध कारणबाट विद्यालय शिक्षाबाट वञ्चित रहेका छन् । त्यसैले शिक्षामा समान अवसरको सट्टा समतामूलक पहुँचको नीति अगाडी सारियो । यस नीतिले गर्दा समाजमा शिक्षाबाट वञ्चित वर्गको विशेष माग अनुसार शैक्षिक रणनीतिहरू विकास गरेर उनीहरूलाई विद्यालय भित्र समाहित गराउने वातावरणको सृजना गर्दछ । जस्तै ः छात्रवृत्ति, सचेतना, मातृभाषामा शिक्षा, समावेशी शिक्षा आदि ।

समाजिक न्याय प्रबद्धन, विद्यार्थी कल्याण समर्थन, सिकाइ परिणाम बढाउन र विद्यार्थीहरूलाई भविष्यको लागि तयार गर्ने जस्ता समतामूलक शिक्षाको प्रमुख सिद्धान्त रहेको छ ।

समावेशी र समतामूलक शिक्षा प्राप्तिका उपायहरू ः-

- अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क शिक्षाको कार्य ढाँचा तयार गरी कार्यान्वयन गर्ने ।
- शिक्षाको अवसरबाट वञ्चित बालबालिका तथा समूहको पहिचान गर्ने ।
- वञ्चित बालबालिका र वर्गलाई शिक्षामा समाहित गर्न कार्यक्रम बनाई कार्यान्वयन गर्ने

माथिका उपायहरू तत्कालमा गर्न सकिने खालका छन् । स्थानीय तहले कार्यान्वयनको लागि दीर्घकालिन नीति, योजना, रणनीति आदि तय गर्नु पर्छ । यसको आधारमा प्रदेश सरकार र संघीय सरकारसँग आवश्यक सहयोगको लागि पहल गर्नु पर्छ ।

अन्तमा, समावेशी र समतामूलक शिक्षाले समाजिक एकतालाई बढावा दिएर, मानव अधिकारको प्रबद्धन गरेर र अझ न्यायपूर्ण समाज निर्माण गरेर समुदाय र राष्ट्र दुबैलाई फाइदा पुऱ्याउँछ ।

मधेश विश्वविद्यालय र मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालयको ऐन संशोधनमा आवश्यकता

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लेखसार

मधेश प्रदेश शिक्षा नीति २०८१ को नीति ७.१२.३ अनुसार दक्ष र गुणस्तरीय जनशक्ति उत्पादनका लागि एकीकृत विश्वविद्यालय सेवा आयोग गठन गरी प्रभावकारी व्यवस्थापन गर्नुपर्ने स्पष्ट नीति रहेको छ। यसले हालका तीनवटा विश्वविद्यालयका छुट्टाछुट्टै विकास समितिहरूको सट्टा एकीकृत सेवा आयोगमार्फत कम खर्चिलो र प्रभावकारी व्यवस्थापन सम्भव बनाउनेछ। त्यसैले, तीनवटा विकास समितिलाई पूर्णरूपमा खारेज गरी एकीकृत सेवा आयोग गठन गर्नुपर्ने अत्यावश्यकता छ।

थप रूपमा, नीति ७.१३ को उपधारा १ र ३ अनुसार राष्ट्रिय योग्यता प्रारूप (National Qualification Framework) अनुसार ड्रपआउट विद्यार्थीहरूलाई पुनः मानवपुँजीमा परिणत गरी श्रमिकलाई सम्मान प्रदान गर्ने र सामाजिक तथा आर्थिक रूपान्तरणमा योगदान पुऱ्याउने कदम अपरिहार्य छ। यसले मधेश प्रदेशमा शिक्षा र रोजगारलाई जोड्ने महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका निर्वाह गर्नेछ।

उच्च शिक्षामा विद्यार्थी भर्ना अनुपात वृद्धि गर्न, रोजगारमूलक शिक्षा प्रणाली विकास गर्न, र आवश्यक मानवपुँजी निर्माणका लागि सिपमूलक शिक्षा प्रदान गर्न नीति ७.१२ को उपधारा १ तथा ३ लाई कार्यान्वयन गर्न आवश्यक छ। यसै सन्दर्भमा, मधेश विश्वविद्यालयको संगठनात्मक स्वरूपमा सिप विद्यालयलाई समेट्ने विषय पनि महत्वपूर्ण छ, जसले प्रदेशको दक्ष जनशक्ति उत्पादनलाई थप मजबुत बनाउनेछ।

मधेश विश्वविद्यालयमा "४पी" रोग: पब्लिकबाट पेमेन्ट, प्राइभेटका लागि प्रदर्शन

मधेश विश्वविद्यालयले हाल "४पी" (Payment from Public and Performance for Private) भन्ने रोगबाट पीडित छ। यसले सार्वजनिक कोषलाई निजी स्वार्थका लागि दुरुपयोग गर्ने र प्रशासनिक अक्षमतालाई जनाउँछ। जनताको पैसाबाट वित्तीय लाभ लिइए पनि सेवा प्रदान गर्ने क्षमता र गुणस्तरमा ठूलो कमी देखिन्छ। यो अवस्थाले विश्वविद्यालयको विश्वसनीयतामा ठूलो प्रहार गरेको छ।

विशेष ध्यान दिनुपर्ने कुरा के हो भने, हाल मधेश विश्वविद्यालय र मधेश कृषि विश्वविद्यालयको नेतृत्वमा त्यस्ता व्यक्ति छन् जो शोध आधारित व्याख्याता पदको लागि तोकिएको योग्यता पूरा गरेर समेत आवेदन दिन सक्दैनन्। यस्तो अवस्थाले विश्वविद्यालयको शैक्षिक गुणस्तर र प्रशासनमा ठूलो असर पारिरहेको छ। यसले विश्वविद्यालयको नेतृत्वमा योग्य र अनुभवी व्यक्तिहरूको आवश्यकता अझ स्पष्ट बनाएको छ।

संशोधनका क्रममा विश्वविद्यालय प्रशासनमा पनि सुधार आवश्यक छ। उपकुलपतिलाई शिक्षण, अनुसन्धान र प्रशासनमा पर्याप्त अनुभव भएको व्यक्ति नियुक्त गर्नुपर्ने व्यवस्था गर्नुपर्नेछ। साथै, विश्वविद्यालयका डीन र रजिष्ट्रार पदमा प्राध्यापक वा सहप्राध्यापकको योग्यता आवश्यक ठहर गर्दै प्रशासनिक दक्षता सुनिश्चित गर्नुपर्नेछ। स्कुल तथा अन्य निकायको अनुभव विश्वविद्यालय प्रशासनमा प्रभावकारी नहुन सक्ने भएकाले विश्वविद्यालयकै अनुभवी कर्मचारी र व्यवस्थापन आवश्यक छ।

यसरी, मधेश प्रदेश शिक्षा नीतिका महत्वपूर्ण धाराहरूलाई प्रभावकारी रूपमा कार्यान्वयन गरी एकीकृत सेवा आयोग गठन, मानवपुँजी विकास, रोजगारमूलक शिक्षा प्रवर्द्धन र प्रशासनिक सुधारमार्फत मधेश प्रदेशका विश्वविद्यालयहरूलाई गुणस्तरीय र समृद्ध बनाउने दिशा तय गर्न आवश्यक छ। सम्बन्धित सबै सरोकारवालाहरूले ऐन संशोधन र नीति कार्यान्वयनमा सक्रिय भूमिका निर्वाह गर्नुपर्ने समय आएको छ।

हामी सबैले मिलेर मधेश प्रदेशको शैक्षिक र आर्थिक समृद्धिका लागि विश्वविद्यालय ऐन संशोधन र प्रभावकारी व्यवस्थापनको लागि आवाज उठाउनुपर्ने बेला आएको छ।

मुख्य शब्दावली : ऐन संशोधन, एकीकृत विश्वविद्यालय सेवा, अनुभव, राष्ट्रिय योग्यता प्रारूप, ४पी (पब्लिकबाट पेमेन्ट, प्राइभेटका लागि प्रदर्शन

दिगो बिकास लक्ष्य पुरा गर्न सहयोग

हरेराम ठाकुर

आसमान नेपाल

लेखसार

आसमान नेपाल र बरहथवा नगरपालिका, सर्लाहीसंगको समन्वय तथा सहकार्यमा नेपाल सरकारको दिगो बिकास लक्ष्यको लक्ष्य नं. ४, गुणस्तरीय शिक्षा अन्तर्गत विद्यालय बाहिर रहेका बालबालिकाहरूलाई विद्यालय तथा शिक्षामा पहुच पुर्याउन, विद्यालय भर्ना दर बढाउन र विद्यालयमा टिकाउन, विद्यालय सरोकारवालाहरूको क्षमता अभिवृद्धिको साथै नगरपालिकाको नीति निर्माण तथा जारी गर्ने कार्यमा सहयोग पुर्याउने लक्ष्यका साथ संचालित शिक्षाद्वारा विद्यालय बाहिर रहेका किशोरीहरूको शसक्तिकरण (बालिकालाई पछाडी नपारौं) परियोजना अन्तर्गत ए.एल.पी सेन्टर (सिघ्र सिकाई कार्यक्रम) को किशोरी सिकाई केन्द्रको साथै विभिन्न क्रियाकलापहरू सर्लाही जिल्लाको बरहथवा नगरपालिकामा संचालित रहेको छ ।

यस किशोरी सिकाई केन्द्र मार्फत नेपाल सरकारले तयार गरेको पाठ्यक्रम अनुसार विद्यालय बाहिर रहेका ८ देखि १८ वर्ष उमेरका किशोरीहरूलाई केन्द्रमा १० देखि ११ महिनासम्म उनीहरूलाई सिकाईको माध्यमले शसक्तबनाई विद्यालयबाट ती किशोरीहरूको प्रवेश परिक्षा लिई सिकाई अनुसार मापनको आधारमा सम्बन्धीत कक्षामा भर्ना गराई उनीहरूलाई विद्यालयमा पहुंच पुर्याउने कार्य हदै आएको छ । यस कार्यले नेपाल सरकारको दिगो बिकास लक्ष्यको लक्ष्य नं. ४, गुणस्तरीय शिक्षा अन्तर्गत विद्यालयबाहिर रहेका किशोरीहरूलाई विद्यालय तथा शिक्षामा पहुंच पुर्याउनुको साथै, विद्यालय भर्ना दर बृद्धि तथा विद्यालय सरोकारवालाहरूको क्षमता अभिवृद्धि गर्ने लक्ष्यलाई पुरा गर्न सहयोग गरेको देखिन्छ ।

किशोरी शिकाई केन्द्रको साथै संचालित विभिन्न क्रियाकलापहरू स्थानिय सरकार तथा स्थानिय सरोकारवालाहरूबाट निरन्तर अनुगमन तथा मुल्यांकन गरी सल्लाह, सुझाव तथा सहयोग भइरहेकाले यो कार्य सफलताका साथ अगाडी बढी रहेको अवस्था छ । स्थानिय सरकारबाट यो परियोजनालाई अतन्त्यतै चासोको रूपमा लिएको अवस्था रहेको छ । हाल सम्म २३२ जना विद्यालय बाहिर रहेका किशोरीहरूलाई विद्यालय तथा शिक्षामा पहुंच पुर्याउन सफल भएको छ र यो कार्य निरन्तर चलिरहेको छ ।

यस परियोजना अन्तर्गत विद्यालय सरोकारवालाहरू, अभिभावक तथा स्थानिय सरोकारवालाहरूको क्षमता अभिवृद्धि तथा सशक्त बनाउनुको साथै नगरपालिकालाई विभिन्न नीति, कार्यविधि बनाई जारी गर्ने कार्यमा पनि आसमान नेपालले प्राविधिक सहयोग गर्दै आएको छ र हालसम्म बालअधिकार संरक्षण, लैंगिक समानता तथा समाजिक समावेशीकरण र बालिका तथा समावेशी शिक्षा संजाल गठन तथा परिचालन कार्यविधि गरी ३ वाटा कार्यविधि जारी भएको छ ।

मुख्य शब्दावली : किशोरीहरू , क्रियाकलापहरू,

प्रति बच्चा अनुगमन (समावेशी तथा समतामूलक शिक्षा)

दिनेश्वर साह

आसमान नेपाल जनकपुरधाम

लेखसार

शिक्षा विकासको मेरुदण्ड हो र बाहिरी संसार चियाउने तेस्रो आँखा पनि । शिक्षा बालबालिकाको नैसर्गिक अधिकार हो । नेपाल बालअधिकार महासन्धी १९८९ को पक्ष राष्ट्र भई बालअधिकार संरक्षणको लागि प्रतिबद्धतछ । भने नेपालको संविधान २०७२ ले शिक्षालाई आधारभूत संवैधानिक अधिकारको रूपमा स्वीकार गरेकोछ । दिगो विकास लक्ष्य २०३० र अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क आधारभूत शिक्षा ऐन २०७५ अनुसार वि.सं. २०८४ सम्ममा सबैलाई आधारभूत शिक्षा सुनिश्चित गर्न सरकारले विभिन्न सरकारी, गैरसरकारी तथा निजीक्षेत्रसंगको समन्वय सहयोग र सहकार्यमा शिक्षाक्षेत्र सुधारको लागि कार्यहरू गर्दै आइरहेकोछ ।

तैपनि आर्थिक, सामाजिक र सांस्कृतिकरूपले अभावग्रस्त सिमानकृत, विपन्न परिवारका बालबालिका, अपांगता भएका २१ प्रतिशत भन्दा बढि बालबालिकाहरू विभिन्न कारणले आधारभूत शिक्षाबाट बञ्चित रहेकाछन् । यसले हाम्रो शिक्षा अझ पनि समावेशी तथा समतामूलक हुन नसक्नुको एउटा सूचक हो । मधेश प्रदेशमा यसको स्थिति अझ भयावहछ । अतः सबैको लागि अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क आधारभूत शिक्षाको सुनिश्चितताको लागि सरकारको प्राथमिकतालाई मनन् गरि बालबालिकाको शिक्षाको अधिकार सुनिश्चित गर्न समुदाय परिचालनको माध्यमबाट प्रति बच्चा अनुगमन गर्न आवश्यक देखिन्छ । यस विधिले प्रतयेक नागरिकको घरघरमा गइ सबै बालबालिकाहरूको गणना र अभिलेख तयार

गर्नुको साथै उनीहरूको पारिवारिक पृष्ठभूमी एवं प्रत्येक बालबालिकाको आवश्यकता अनुसार योजना बनाई काम गर्न सहयोग गर्दछ ।

यसका लागि माध्यमिक तथा उच्च शिक्षामा अध्ययनरत युवाहरूलाई स्थानीय पालिकाबाट छनौट र वडाको मातहतमा रहने गरि शिक्षा स्वयंसेवक ÷ बडकी दिदीको रूपमा काम गर्ने अवसर दिइनेछ । यिनीहरूले विद्यालय जानबाट बञ्चित बालबालिकाहरूको अभिलेख अनुसार विद्यालय भर्ना तथा नियमित गराउने कामको साथै तिनीहरूका परिवारमा नियमित घरभेट गरि सकारात्मक अभिभावकत्वको लागि आवश्यक परामर्श सेवा प्रदान गर्ने र बालबालिकाहरूको विशेष आवश्यकतानुसार उपयुक्त शैक्षिक संस्थाहरूमा रेफर गर्ने काममा स्थानीय सरकारलाई सहयोग गर्नेछन् । अन्ततः शिक्षालाई समावेशी तथा समतामूलक बनाउन र शतप्रतिशत विद्यालय भर्ना स्थानीय तह घोषणाको कार्यमा यिनीहरूले महत्वपूर्ण योगदान गर्नेछन् ।

जसले युवाहरूमा आफ्नो समुदायको लागि सेवा गर्ने भावना जागृत गराउन सकिनेछ । स्थानीय सरकारले यी शिक्षा स्वयंसेवकहरूलाई निश्चित तालिम, प्रबन्धिय सामाग्री सहयोग र न्युनतम आर्थिक सहयोग गरि रचनात्मक कार्यका लागि सेवा नै धर्म हो भन्ने भावनालाई प्रोत्साहित गर्नेछन् । यस कार्यको लागि स्थानीय स्तरमा काम गर्ने गैरसरकारी, सरकारी तथा निजी संघसंस्थाहरूसंग समन्वय, सहयोग र सहकार्य गर्न सकिनेछ ।

कोई नइ छुटे, एकसाथ जुटे ! सबकोई पढु आगा बढु ! प्रत्येक बच्चाके गणना होइ !

प्रत्येक स्थानीय तह एक स्थानीय संग्रहालय

दिनेश्वर साह

आसमान नेपाल जनकपुरधाम

लेखसार

कुनै पनि व्यक्ति वा समुदायको पहिचान त्यसले अंगालेको भाषा, संस्कृति, साहित्य र कलाबाट हुने भएकोले भाषा तथा संस्कृतिको अति महत्व रहेकोछ । नेपाल बहुभाषिक, बहुसांस्कृतिक राष्ट्र हो । धार्मिक तथा सांस्कृतिक विविधतामा एकता र सहअस्तित्व नै यहाँको विशेषता हो । मधेश प्रदेश आफैमा एक विविधता र विशेषताले भरेको प्रदेश हो । यहाँ मैथिली, भोजपुरी, बज्जिका, मगही, नेपाली, हिन्दी, थारु, मगर लगायत विभिन्न भाषा बोल्ने मानिसहरु बसोबास गर्दछन् । तिनीहरुको आफ्नै भाषा, धर्म, कला, संस्कृति, रितिरिवाज, भेषभुषा, रहनसहन, खानपान आदि रहेकोछ । यिनै विविधतायुक्त संस्कार र सभ्यताले यस प्रदेशलाई जीवन्त एवं गतिशिल बनाएकोछ ।

विश्वव्यापीकरण र सूचनासंचारको प्रविधिमा भएको विकास एवं विस्तारले यसक्षेत्रको दायरा अझ फराकिलो बनाएकोछ भने आयातित भाषा, संस्कृति तथा संरक्षणको अभावमा धेरै कुराहरु संकटमा परेको र लोपोन्मुख अवस्थामा रहेकोछ । यी सबैको संबर्धन, संरक्षण र विकासको गर्नु हामी सबैको दायित्व हो र यो हाम्रो संवैधानिक हक पनि जसलाई नेपालको संविधान २०७२ ले सुनिश्चित गरेकोछ । ऐतिहासिक अवस्थाबारे जान्न बुझ्न र अध्ययन अनुसन्धान गरि नयाँ पुस्तमा ज्ञानको हस्तान्तरणको अपरिहार्यतले यसको संरक्षण, संबर्धन, विकास र विस्तारको लागि प्रत्येक स्थानीय तह एक स्थानीय संग्रहालय आजको आवश्यकता हो ।

प्रत्येक स्थानीय तह एक स्थानीय संग्रहालयले स्थानी तहमा रहेका समुदायका मानिसको जीवन प्रणालीसंग जोडिएका ऐतिहासिक र वर्तमान कला, संस्कृति, भेषभुषा, कृषि, स्वास्थ्य,

शिक्षा, धर्म, सूचना प्रविधि लगायत जीवनयापनसंग सम्बन्धित विविध पक्षहरूको अभिलेख, सामाग्रीहरूको संकलन र व्यवस्थापन गरि ज्ञानको विकास, विस्तार र संबर्धन गरि प्रयोगको लागि प्रोत्साहन गर्नेछन् । यसको लागि स्थानीय तहले मौजुदावस्थामा रहेको पुस्तकालय, बाचनालय, शैक्षिक संस्था तथा सार्वजनिक भवनलाई प्रयोग गरि स्थानीय समुदायको सहयोगमा उपरोक्त सामाग्रीहरूको संकलन र व्यवस्थापन गर्न सक्नेछन् । यसको निरन्तरता तथा व्यवस्थापनको लागि विद्यार्थीहरू, प्रतिभावान व्यक्तित्व तथा स्थानीय समुदायका नवश्रृजनाहरूको सहयोग लिन सकिन्छ । यसरी संकलित र श्रृजित सामाग्रीहरूले त्यस क्षेत्रको कला, संस्कृतिको संरक्षण, संबर्धन र अध्ययन अनुसन्धानमा सहयोग गर्नुको साथै स्थानीय पर्यटनमा समेत सहयोग पुर्याइ त्यस क्षेत्रको नयाँ पहिचानलाई स्थापित गर्न सहायक हनेछन् । यसको लागि प्रदेश सरारले आवश्यक सहयोग, समन्वय र सहजीकरण गरि स्थानीय तहलाई प्रोत्साहित गर्न अपरिहार्य हुन आउँछ ।

कला संस्कृति हमर पहिचान, हमर सभ्यता हमर स्वाभिमान ! हमर भाषा हमर भेष, विविध संस्कृति सुदृढ प्रदेश !

शिक्षा स्वयंसेवक (शिक्षामा श्रोत परिचालन तथा दिगोपन)

दिनेश्वर साह

आसमान नेपाल जनकपुरधाम

लेखसार

शिक्षा विकासको मेरुदण्ड हो र बाहिरी संसार चियाउने तेस्रो आँखा पनि । र त शिक्षालाई आधारभूत संवैधानिक अधिकारको रूपमा स्थापित गरिएको छ । यद्यपि २१औं शताब्दिमा आएर पनि विश्वका ७५४ मिलियन, ३२ मिलियन एशियामा र नेपालमा झण्डै ७२ लाख मानिसहरू शिक्षाको अधिकारबाट बन्चित रहेको अवस्था छ । नेपाल सरकारको जीवनस्तर प्रतिवेदन २०२२ अनुसार नेपालमा १७ वर्षमुनिका करिब २१ प्रतिशत बालबालिकाहरू अझ पनि विभिन्न कारणले आधारभूत शिक्षाबाट बञ्चित छन् भने २४ प्रतिशत नागरिकहरू साक्षर हुन नसकेको अवस्था छ ।

दिगो विकास लक्ष्य २०३० भित्र सबै नागरिकले आधारभूत शिक्षा उपलब्ध गराइ सक्नु पर्ने अन्तर्राष्ट्रिय प्रतिबद्धता अनुसार वि.सं. २०८४ सम्म सबैलाई आधारभूत शिक्षा सुनिश्चित गर्न सरकारले अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क आधारभूत शिक्षा लगायतका रणनीति तथा योजनाहरू बनाएर विभिन्न सरकारी, गैरसरकारी तथा निजीक्षेत्रको सहयोगमा शिक्षाक्षेत्र सुधारको लागि कार्यहरू गर्दै आइरहेका छन् ।

अतः नेपाल सरकारले विभिन्न मञ्चमा गरेको प्रतिबद्धता, शिक्षाको दशवर्षे रणनीति र सबैको लागि अनिवार्य तथा निःशुल्क आधारभूत शिक्षाको सुनिश्चितताको लागि सरकारको प्राथमिकतालाई मनन् गरि नागरिकको शिक्षाको अधिकार पुरा गर्ने कामको लागि जनस्तरमा काम गर्न एक वडा एक शिक्षा स्वयंसेवकको अबधारणा ल्याईएको हो । खासमा निरक्षर

नागरिकलाई साक्षर बनाउने र विद्यालय जानबाट बञ्चित बालबालिकाहरूका विद्यालय भर्ना तथा नियमित गराउने काममा सहयोग गर्ने यसको मुख्य जिम्मेवारी रहनेछ । यी शिक्षा स्वयंसेवकहरू स्थानीय पालिकाबाट छनौट भइ वडाको मातहतमा रहने गरि काम गर्नेछन् । साक्षर पालिका र शतप्रतिशत विद्यालय भर्ना स्थानीय तह घोषणाको कार्यमा यिनीहरूले महत्वपूर्ण योगदान गर्नेछन् ।

पालिकामा छनौट हुने शिक्षा स्वयंसेवकहरूमा माध्यमिक तथा उच्च शिक्षामा अध्ययनरत एवं अवकाश प्राप्त शिक्षक तथा कर्मचारीहरूलाई अवसर दिइनेछ । यसबाट दक्ष तथा अनुभवी जनशक्तिको सदुपयोग हुनेछ भने युवाहरूमा आफ्नो समुदायको लागि सेवागर्ने भावना जागृत गराउन मदत मिल्नेछ । स्थानीय सरकारले यी शिक्षा स्वयंसेवकहरूलाई निश्चित तालिम, प्रबन्धिय सामग्री सहयोग र न्युनतम आर्थिक सहयोग गरि रचनात्मक कार्यका लागि सेवा नै धर्म हो भन्ने भावनाका साथ अन्य क्षेत्रहरूमा पनि प्रोत्साहित गर्न सक्नेछन् । यस कार्यको लागि स्थानीय स्तरमा काम गर्ने गैरसरकारी, सरकारी तथा निजी संघसंस्थाहरूसंग समन्वय, सहयोग र सहकार्य गर्न सकिनेछ ।

पढु मधेशी बढु मधेशी ! पढ्दै मधेश, पढ्दै मधेश ! ज्ञान दान, महा कल्याण !

Book of Abstract

Madhesh Province Government

मधेश प्रदेश सरकार
शिक्षा तथा संस्कृति मन्त्रालय
जनकपुरधाम, मधेश प्रदेश